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Online Appendixes for Productivity Impulses from Regional Integration: Lessons from Road Openings¹

A.Appendix: Background on the Study Region

In this appendix, we elaborate on the study region, extending our presentation and discussions from subsection 2.1. We start by reviewing studies and documents indicating that productivity concerns have played a limited role in the selection of Norwegian road construction projects. Thereafter, we go more into depth on the expansion of the road network in our study region of Coastal Southern Norway.

A.1 Lack of Productivity Concerns in Selection of Norwegian Road Construction Projects

Since the turn of the millennium, wider economic impacts have become gradually more important in economic appraisal in developed countries (confer Holmen, Biesinger and Hindriks 2020). While national appraisal guidelines for transportation accounted for wider economic impacts in Odgaard, Kelly and Laird (2005), two thirds of the countries included these impacts in Wangsness, Rødseth and Hansen (2016). While both the American and British guidelines involved methods for quantification of wider economic impacts based on market access of different industries at the time (e.g. Department for Transport 2014 and Weisbrod et al. 2014), these impacts were still not accounted for in the Norwegian appraisal guidance.

The Norwegian Ministry of Finance's comprehensive scheme for impact assessment of infrastructure investments including cost-benefit analyses is mandatory for projects above a certain fiscal limit. During our study period, this limit was NOK 1 billion in current prices. So far, productivity potential has neither been accounted for as a monetarized impact nor a non-monetarized impact in public Norwegian cost-benefit analyses. At the turn of the millennium, the main objectives in the Norwegian national guidance for planning of national and county routes were to ensure efficient, safe and environmentally friendly transportation. Wider economic impacts are mentioned only once as a factor to ensure these objectives without being specified further (Norwegian Ministry of Environment and Norwegian Ministry of Transportation and Communications 1994). Neither the Norwegian Ministry of Finance's (2005) nor the Norwegian Public Road Administration's (2006a) guidelines for cost-benefit

¹ The paper: Holmen, R. B. (2022). Productivity Impulses from Regional Integration: Lessons from Road Openings. *Insights into Regional Development*, 4(4), 83-125. [http://doi.org/10.9770/IRD.2022.4.4\(6\)](http://doi.org/10.9770/IRD.2022.4.4(6))

analysis valid from 2005 and 2006 to 2014 include assessment of broader economic impacts from road constructions such as potential productivity effects.

Two expert committees appointed by the Norwegian Ministry of Finance (1997 and 2012) recommended that ripple effects from infrastructure construction should not be included in cost-benefit analyses of infrastructure due to uncertainty and possible pressure from lobbyists. Several authors criticize the Norwegian National Transportation Plan for random order of priority and lack of overall objectives (e.g. Eliasson et al. 2015, Strand et al. 2015 and Norwegian Ministry of Finance 2015).

Several studies indicate that economic appraisal has been less important for investment decisions in road projects in Norway than in Denmark and Sweden (Boge 2006, Eliasson et al. 2015, Welde et al. 2013 and Wangsness et al. 2016). In their econometric investigation, Eliasson et al. (2015) find that the realization of Swedish road projects required positive benefit-cost ratios – while the benefit-cost ratio had no impact on Norwegian road projects whatsoever, even in case of projects with benefit-cost ratios well below unity. Overall, Holmen, Biesinger and Hindriks' (2020) review on decision processes in various countries suggests that Norway is among the countries where economic appraisal has the least practical impact (see also PIARC 2003).

In Norway, each major road investment constitutes a national matter, typically with financing contributions from both central and local governments. Both in parliament and in the county councils, rural regions are overrepresented compared to population share to ensure these regions' interests. Findings in the literature suggest that the political decisions leading up to the national allocation of road investments in Norway have to a limited extent been based on productivity potential in particular or cost-benefit assessments in general (Welde et al. 2013, Eliasson et al. 2015, Strand et al. 2015 and Sager 2016). A general finding is that Norwegian road investments have been distributed according to regional policy and traffic safety concerns rather than other cost-benefit considerations (e.g. Elvik 1995, Nyborg and Spangen 1996, Boge 2006, Helland and Sørensen 2009 and Odeck 2010).

Strand (1983 and 1993) shows that the distribution for Norwegian road investments over Norwegian counties is stable over time – a finding which is later confirmed by Nyborg and Spangen (1996) and Strand et al. (2015). Interviewing members of the Committee on Transport and Communications at the Storting (i.e. the Norwegian Parliament), Nyborg and Spangen (1996) find that national politicians considered information from lobbyists and local politicians important for their basis for decisions. Many representatives considered the fixed distribution shares between counties a challenge and said they lacked information on impacts on the business sector. Few members of parliament said that cost-benefit analysis plays an important role for their views, and many of them stated that it did not matter to them. In their qualitative investigation, Eliasson et al. (2015) find that Norwegian and Swedish politicians tend to favor investments in regions with strong local support, while bureaucrats were much more inclined to take benefit-cost ratios into consideration, and also particularly high costs. Elvik (1995) concludes that the distribution of road investments between Norwegian counties is explained by road standard and vote trading rather than net benefit assessments.

Studying the low economic return on Norwegian road projects, Halse and Fridstrøm (2018) reveal that projects in remote areas and in areas with difficult topography have lower net benefits. Odeck (1996), Fridstrøm and Elvik (1997) and Eliasson et al. (2015) find that high net

benefit for road investments for rural counties slightly increases their probability to be selected, but it is far from the most decisive factor for projects being picked. Yet, productivity is not a focus area in these net benefit assessments. Halse (2016) finds that road investments are lower when politicians represent large populations. Sager (2016) finds that the list of prioritized projects changes little after consultants' and researchers' submission of cost-benefit analyses to national politicians due to vested political interests and solid state-finances. Reviewing future projects in the Norwegian National Transportation Plan applying qualitative and quantitative methods, Strand et al. (2015) confirm that cost-benefit analyses are not decisive for project prioritization in practice. Multiple studies find that assessment of Norwegian road investment projects at state level puts little weight on non-monetized impacts and particularly non-monetized benefits such as potential productivity impacts (Rasmussen et al. 2010, Norwegian Public Road Administration 2012, Lædre et al. 2012 and Bull-Berg et al. 2014).

A.2 Expansion of the Road Network in Southern Norway

Today's European Routes 18 and 39 in Southern Norway largely follow the Western Norwegian Main Road (later renamed the Southern Norwegian Main Road) built in the 1800s for horses and carts along the main route from Oslo to Stavanger (Irgens 1978). Due to historical fear of sabotage in case of war, many of the main road segments along the coast of Southern Norway were kept inland and did not lead through the coastal towns. The modern European Routes 18 and 39 were largely built in the 1960s and gradually connected as a trunk road network up to the 1970s. A considerable change was that the main road was redirected to go directly from Lillesand to Kristiansand, instead of taking a detour through Birkenes. In addition, in the period up to the early 1990s the routes are gradually redirected outside some of the town centers rather than through them, also due to urban environmental concerns.

On European Route 18, the route segments in the middle of Aust-Agder county were upgraded to trunk road last. The trunk road between Lunde and Rømyr, both in Tvedestrand municipality, was not finished before 1996. In the 1990s, new highway segments were built in Grimstad and between Bie and Temse, both in Grimstad municipality, and between Østerholt in Risør municipality and Høgslø in Gjerstad municipality. On today's European Route 39 (which before 27th of May 1997 was a part of European Route 18), many updates were carried out across the route during the 1980s.

As accounted for in subsection 2.1 the substantial road construction projects in our study case were organized through four road packages – in connection with European Route 18 in the eastern parts of our study region, to the Kristiansand Package in the middle of our study region and to European Route 19 and the Lister Package in western Parts of our study region. The Setesdal region in the non-coastal part of Aust-Agder was little affected by the road constructions and was instead granted an own package (i.e. the Setesdal Package, confer Norwegian Ministry of Transport and Communications 2002a and Transportation and Communications Committee at the Storting 2002a).

The renewal of European Route 18 in Southern Norway started in the early 2000s. In 2001, European Route 18 was renewed from Gartnerløkka to Timenes in the eastern part of Kristiansand municipality, while a highway segment between Temse in Grimstad municipality and Rannekleiv in Arendal municipality was opened. A fourth major road construction in our study region occurred at European Route 18 20th of August 2004 between Vinterkjær in Risør municipality and Brokelandsheia in Gjerstad municipality, including the 'Pinesund Bridge'

above lake Molandsvannet. The route constitutes the main artery from Coastal Southern Norway to Kragerø municipality and the rest of Eastern Norway. The construction project reduced traveling time on the route by 6 minutes, from 44 to 38 minutes. Travel from Gjerstad to Risør municipality center requires a detour to Risør on County Route 416 in Aust-Agder, while the municipality center in Tvedestrand, south of Risør, lies next to European Route 18, Tvedestrand. As the traveling time to Gjerstad and further north was not very different than for Risør, Tvedestrand municipality was affected nearly as much. Yet, as the project was implemented already in the first year of our study period (which happens to be the first year with reliable geo-tagged firm data), its impact on our study is likely to be more moderate.

Subsequently, the route segment on European Route 18 in Aust-Agder between Øygardsdalen in Grimstad municipality and Rona in Kristiansand municipality was prioritized due to a large maintenance backlog on the route (Norwegian Ministry of Transport and Communications 1997a and Transportation and Communications Committee at the Storting 1997a). On 26th of August 2009, the renewed route segment was opened, inducing a traveling time reduction of 12 minutes from 34 to 22 minutes. The route segment goes through Lillesand's commuting routes to Kristiansand and Grimstad, cutting traveling times by 4 and 8 minutes respectively. The road opening also induced similar traveling time reductions between Birkeland, the center of Birkenes municipality, and Grimstad. Furthermore, it decreased the traveling time between Birkenes and Kristiansand through County Route 402 in Aust-Agder and European Route 18 to about the traveling time at the fastest route between the two locations at National Route 41.

In proximity to Kristiansand, the renewal of the road also contributed to some queueing time reductions in the rush hours (but as we have accounted for in subsection 3.2, we have omitted such traveling time reductions from our dataset due to endogeneity concerns in relation to economic outcomes). Simultaneously, the speed limit at the continuation of the road to Harebakken in Arendal was increased, reducing traveling time on this route by an additional minute from 24 to 23 minutes. Note that this road construction project distinguishes itself from the others in the sense that it is located in the most populated area of Southern Norway.

The rest of the renewal of European Route 39 in Southern Norway was delayed due to a slow planning process for the whole road at a national level and somewhat less urgent maintenance needs. According to current construction plans, the renewal of the road will start on the route segments near Kristiansand as a part of a new Kristiansand Package (Norwegian Ministry of Transport and Communications 1997a and Transportation and Communications Committee at the Storting 1997a). In the early 2000s, some maintenance work was carried out on the route between Søgne and Kristiansand in the eastern part of Vest-Agder county, but most of the road investments took place in the western part of the county.

The Lister Package in the western region of Lister was granted to improve relatively poor road standards in the area. According to the decision documents, European Route 39 between Handeland in Lyngdal municipality and Feda in Kvinesdal municipality and County Route 465 in Vest-Agder from Feda in Kvinesdal municipality to Sande in Farsund municipality were prioritized due to large maintenance backlogs and many accidents. The new route between Handeland in Lyngdal municipality to Feda in Kvinesdal municipality was opened 30th of August 2006. It reduced the traveling time on the route by 14 minutes, from 37 to 23 minutes. The construction project included 'Fedafjorden Bridge' across the fjord Fedafjorden (the largest bridge in Southern Norway), in addition to several other bridges and tunnels (i.e. Birkeland

Bridge, Refsti Bridge, Fedahei Tunnel, Lindland Tunnel and Teistedal Tunnel). Officially, the road construction project was labeled ‘European Route 39 Lyngdal – Flekkefjord’, since the largest traveling time reductions induced by the project occurred between Lyngdal and Flekkefjord, and not between Lyngdal and Kvinesdal. It cut the traveling time between Lyngdal and Flekkefjord by 17 minutes, from 46 to 29 minutes, where the three additional minutes in traveling time reductions compared to the main construction segment were caused by increased speed limits and construction of the ‘Lindland Tunnel’.

The renewal of County Route 465 in Vest-Agder between Kjørrefjord in Farsund municipality and Ulland in Kvinesdal municipality was carried out stepwise. In the period from 2009 to 2012, traveling time between these two destinations was cut by 18 minutes, from 52 minutes to 34 minutes. Five minutes’ traveling time reduction was induced 24th of November in 2009 by the opening of the ‘Ravnehei Tunnel’ through the hill Ravneheia in Farsund municipality. On 19th of October 2012, the remaining 13 minutes were realized with the official road opening.

In addition to the traveling time reductions caused by the major road construction projects accounted for above, some small maintenance work and speed limit adjustments changed the traveling times within the region during the study period. In connection with the Lister Package, County Route 43 in Vest-Agder from Aunevik in Farsund municipality and Bukkesteinen in Lyngdal municipality was opened 28th of November 2006, inducing two minutes traveling time reduction. From 2008 to 2013, changes in speed limits gradually gave rise to a traveling time reduction of 5 minutes at County Route 751 in Vest-Agder between Liknes municipality in Kvinesdal and Eiken in Hægebostad municipality. In addition, some new road constructions were opened without involving any significant traveling time reductions, inter alia within the municipalities of Lindesnes and Farsund. Subsequently to our study period, the road segment at European Route 18 between Rømyr in Tvedestrand municipality and Harebakken in Arendal municipality was opened 2nd of July 2019.

Southern Norway’s coastline was little affected by road projects outside the region beyond potential general equilibrium mechanisms. The closest major road constructions outside the region was the renewal of European 18 Langangen in Porsgrunn municipality to Sky in Larvik municipality northeast of our study region, which took place on 6th of June 2012. It only reduced the traveling time on the route by two minutes, from 12 minutes to 11 minutes in addition to queue reduction. The travel time between our study region (i.e. Akland in Risør municipality) and the route segment (i.e. Langangen in Porsgrunn municipality) was 1 hour and 1 minute during the study period. The second major road construction outside the region was the Finnfast mainland connection on National Highway 519 between Vikevåg in Rennesøy municipality and Judaberg in Finnøy municipality, which implied a travel time reduction on the route from 31 to 16 minutes in addition to reduction of discomfort associated with the inflexibility of ferry crossings. The travel time between our study region (i.e. Sira in Flekkefjord municipality) and the route segment (i.e. Vikevåg in Rennesøy municipality) was 118 minutes during the study period. In addition, some projects were implemented in connection with the Setesdal package at Route 9 in Bykland municipality north of the study region, but these did not induce any traveling time reductions. We refer to Norwegian Ministry of Transport and Communications (1993, 1997b, 2000a and 2004a) and Transportation and Communications Committee at the Storting (1993, 1997b, 2000a and 2004) for overview over the decision process related to road constructions implemented in South Norway during our study period.

As discussed in subsection 2.1, earlier studies of Norwegian road investment decisions indicate that the prioritization of construction projects within the study region is largely detached from concerns about productivity potential. Cost-benefit ratios more generally appear to be fairly detached from the decision process – and the timing of the projects even more so. Reviewing the decision documents for the major road projects in Southern Norway during our study period, we do not find conclusive evidence ruling out that productivity potential has been decisive for their realization. The presented arguments in public decision documents focus on traffic mobility and the need for maintenance and improved road standards. They do not mention productivity potential. Yet, direct transportation costs savings and housing and labor market region integration are also presented as arguments in the decision documents, particularly in the most recent ones, concerning the Lister Region (Norwegian Ministry of Transport and Communications 2000a, 2002b and 2004b, Norwegian Public Road Administration 2006b, 2007, 2008a and 2008b, Transportation and Communications Committee at the Storting 1997a and 2005 and Terramar 2004 and Vianova 2008 for European Route 18 in Agder, and Norwegian Ministry of Transport and Communications 2002b and Transportation and Communications Committee at the Storting 2002b for the projects in the Lister Region).

Moreover, the Norwegian Public Road Administration's main objectives for the new route at European Route 18 were 'to reduce economic transportation costs', 'to reduce the accident level', 'to ensure high and even road standard that increases traffic mobility', 'to protect culture and natural environments' and 'biological diversity along the road and to solve the existing environmental issues along the existing route' (Terramar 2004). Terramar (2004) delivered its quality assurance of the road construction project September 2004, organized as a public-private-partnership project. The consultancy found that the planning of the project was satisfactory, but it saw a need for further processing and concretizing of the projects' stated objectives. Although these arguments are mentioned in the formal documents, they may not have affected the prioritization order of the projects. Moreover, there may also be a wedge between the formal arguments represented in these documents and the informal arguments that proved decisive for the political decision-making process in practice (Nyborg and Spangen 1996). Nevertheless, the mentioning of these aspects in the decision documents may cast doubt on the exogeneity of the investments in road constructions, so we choose to instrument expansions in the road network.

B. Appendix: Supporting Empirical Examinations

In this appendix, we provide supporting empirical results and analyses on productivity impulses induced by increased market access. The purpose of the appendix is to check for robustness of our baseline results and to investigate the impact of choice of estimation approach.

B.1 Examination on Aggregate Productivity Effects

Before we dig into the details, we find it expedient to look for signs of productivity impulses for the region at aggregate level. Moreover, we will present an introductory investigation of productivity impulses from the road construction in our case study that affected most people (i.e. at European Route 18 between Kristiansand and Grimstad). In our investigation, we find it useful to compare the aggregate productivity growth in the affected municipalities with municipalities of similar characteristics (i.e. degree of urbanization and industry composition).

We start by looking at the development in aggregate labor productivity in all municipalities in our study region by our population reflection method, where the population characteristic matched on is industry composition. As a basis of comparison, we construct a population reflection for each municipality. A municipality's industry reflection tells us what the labor productivity would have been for a benchmark region, if the factor composition had been the same as in the municipality itself and the industry-specific labor productivity remained the same. We express labor productivity $a_{IR(r,b),t}$ for industry reflection $IR(r,b)$ for municipality r based on benchmark region b at time t as:

$$(1) a_{IR(r,b),t} = \sum_{i=1}^N a_{b,i,t} \frac{n_{r,i,t}}{n_{r,t}}$$

where $a_{b,i,t}$ is labor productivity in industry i in benchmark region b at time t , $n_{r,i,t}$ is employment in industry i in municipality r at time t , and $n_{r,t}$ is aggregate employment in region r at time t . Hence, ratio between $n_{r,i,t}$ and $n_{r,t}$ corresponds to the employment share. In the benchmark region, we include all municipalities of our extended study region. We let the employment shares vary over time, but the results are nearly the same when they are fixed to the pretreatment period of each project.²

In Figure B-1, we have shown the results from our investigation on industry reflections. In most cases, the municipalities' aggregate developments in labor productivity follow the developments in their industry reflection rather closely, with some obvious exceptions. Among the municipalities that have been more closely integrated with Kristiansand through the renewal of European Route 18 in August 2009 (i.e. Risør, Tvedestrand, Arendal, Grimstad, Lillesand and Birkenes), the clearest indications of productivity impulses are seen in Lillesand. This is no surprise, considering that it is the municipality where we measure the highest increase in market access (confer subsection 4.2). The municipalities next to Lillesand – Grimstad and Arendal – had a labor productivity just below their industry reflections before the road opening and just above after the road opening, but these tendencies are very weak and barely visible. They are also the largest municipalities in our study region (although Grimstad's settlement is largely located outside the central urban area), so one should expect smaller differences. In case of Kristiansand, the regional city, there is no visible improvement in the figure at all.

² Our population reflection method builds on roughly the same idea as the industry structure control introduced in context of estimation of the market access functions (confer subsection 2.2). It can easily be adjusted to become more suited for pseudo-causal investigations by fixing the industry-specific employment shares to the ones in the pretreatment period and then adjust for aggregate development in the treatment years. p-values could potentially be obtained through bootstrapping, exploiting the outcomes from similar investigations in the municipalities in the benchmark region. In our case, the different municipalities face road openings in their vicinities at different times, if any at all. In the reported figures, we therefore only use the population reflection method to shed light on some descriptive patterns, without fixing the labor shares to the pretreatment period. Yet, our trials with pretreatment matching of industry shares suggests that the picture is rather similar in such approach, since industry structure changes slowly and little in our brief time span. In our causal investigation, we will proceed with the synthetic control method in case of the municipalities with highest potential for causal impacts. Compared to the synthetic control method, the industry reflection method has the advantage that it exploits the whole benchmark sample and is not vulnerable to the selection of benchmark municipalities in the control group. Its comparative disadvantage is that it does not necessarily fulfill the common trend assumption nor take potential synergies between local industries into account.

Figure B-1: Comparison of net value added per person engaged between the municipalities in our study sample and their industry reflections. The second axis is measured in million NOK in fixed prices at average price level from 1999 to 2014.

The renewal of European Route 18 is not visible in the figure for Birkenes, northeast of Kristiansand, which faced some major deficits within the manufacturing industry late in our study period. This municipality did not experience any substantial traveling time reduction towards Kristiansand due to the construction, but the traveling time towards Grimstad and Arendal was reduced some. Northeast in our study region, Risør seemingly shows a relative improvement in labor productivity subsequently to the road opening between Grimstad and Kristiansand, while Tvedestrand does not. The earlier road opening on European Route 18 between Risør and Gjerstad (north in our study region) August 2004 is not visible in the figures. The five municipalities just west of Kristiansand (i.e. Vennesla, Songdalen, Søgne, Mandal and Lindesnes) are neither in immediate proximity to any major road openings, nor do they show any systematic deviations in productivity development from their industry reflections.

In the western part of the study region, (i.e. the Lister Region, which consists of Lyngdal, Farsund, Kvinesdal and Flekkefjord), the figures for Lyngdal and Farsund are both dominated by volatile performance in the local manufacturing industries. The County Route 465 in Vest-Agder towards Kvinesdal was mainly implemented October 2012, but one subsegment was opened November in 2009. Signs of small relative improvement in labor productivity for Farsund after the local road opening are overshadowed by a volatile productivity development. The productivity impulses from the road opening at European Route 39 between Flekkefjord and Lyngdal August 2006 are apparently clear in case of Flekkefjord, which according to our measurement has the largest increase in market access in the Lister Region. The opening of road projects in the Lister Region is neither visible for Lyngdal nor Kvinesdal.

In our further investigations on aggregate productivity given industry structure, we focus on European Route 18, as it constitutes the regional new road constructions occurring in the most inhabited area in our study and thereby the most likely opening to have induced any productivity impulses. We compare the total factor productivity development in the nearby municipalities with municipalities with similar industry structure and development prior to the road opening. The synthetic control method is suitable for this purpose, since it allows researchers to compare an affected treatment unit with a synthetic control unit constructed by potential control units with similar co-variables and pre-treatment trend. While the new road constructions in the Lister Region were dispersed over time and routes, the investments at Aust-Agder were concentrated along European Route 18. The corresponding road opening induced traveling time savings of 12 minutes from Arendal and Grimstad to Kristiansand from August 2009.

In an introductory investigation of the productivity impulses from this major construction, we utilize Abadie, Diamond and Hainmueller (2010) synthetic control method on productivity. We apply the nested optimization procedure that searches among all positive semidefinites to find the best fitting convex combination of the control units. In our practical implementation, we apply the command *synth* in Stata, specifying the option *nested*. By minimizing the mean squared prediction error, the method allows for reweighting of the potential control groups, such that the synthetic control group unit matches productivity and some observed covariates before the treatment period. As productivity measure, we apply net value added-based total factor productivity estimates, which are pre-estimated by Wooldridge's (2009) procedure without any controls, applying Rovigatti and Mollisi's (2018) Stata command, *prodest*. As covariates exploited in matching, we apply pre-treatment industry shares.³

The four municipalities closest to the road opening at European Route 18 – Arendal, Grimstad, Kristiansand and Lillesand – are merged to a common treatment in the baseline approach, where all are weighted equally. We also run the regression analyses separately with each municipality as a treatment unit, where the others are excluded. As potential controls, we include all Norwegian municipalities, except for the most urban and the most rural ones,⁴ and the ones within 30 minutes from a new road construction that induces traveling time reductions of at least five minutes to nearby locations. To ensure a common trend between the treatment unit and the synthetic control unit, we use 2004 to 2008 as pre-treatment period. We use 2010 to

³ We apply the same industry selection as in the rest of our study, as accounted for in subsection 3.1, with A64 second revision as the applied industry division.

⁴ This corresponds to level 2 to 9 in the public Norwegian municipal urbanization index from 1 to 10 (confer Juvkam and Gundersen 2013 for documentation).

2014 as the treatment period. 2009 is neither recognized as a pre-treatment year nor a treatment year, as the opening of the route took place in August that year.

To be able to say something about significance levels, we apply a user-written modification of *synth*, which allows us to perform separate control group. We approximate the p-values by considering how little the treatment units' root mean square prediction errors are, through hypothesis testing (i.e. student t-test in case of one treatment unit and Chow-test in case of several treatment units). To get a more complete impression of deviation of the pre-treatment trend, we also report the pre-treatment standard deviations. Unfortunately, nested synthetic control group regressions were not possible for all municipalities due to lack of convergence, so the somewhat rougher quadratic programming routine in the *synth* program was applied instead for all municipalities for this purpose. The nested routine was also a bit more unstable.

Moreover, the regression results from the synthetic control analyses, as shown in Figure B-2, do not show clear productivity impulses from the road opening at European Route 18. Some regression results are significant within ten percent (i.e. for Arendal, Kristiansand and all four municipalities jointly). Yet, the results for the two municipalities with the highest increases in market access – Lillesand and Grimstad – are not significant. This may reflect that industry's municipal presence and benefits from road openings vary, but it could also reflect that the impulses seen are slim or even spurious. Moreover, the productivity patterns in the figure do not show very clear productivity impulses compared to the control regions, especially in application of the nested routine. Besides, the pre-treatment standard deviations are positive.

Overall, our examination on aggregate productivity impulses given industry composition warrants further inquiries. Yet, it also calls for caution with regard to the interpretation of our results, as alternative explanations and underlying development patterns may come into play.

Figure B-2: Synthetic control regressions for productivity impulses from new European Route 18 on Arendal and Grimstad municipalities compared to comparable municipalities. Depiction of: a) Development in productivity for the treated unit and the synthetic control unit, estimated by a nested programming routine (l.h.s.) and b) development in productivity dispersion between municipalities and their synthetic control, estimated by a quadratic programming routine. Only the treatment unit and potential control units with maximum 50 percent deviation in the pre-treatment trend from the treatment unit's trend are illustrated (r.h.s.).

B.2 Robustness Examination on Firm Productivity

In this subappendix, we consider alternative approaches for studying productivity impulses from increased market access induced by traveling times in the road network to our baseline approach, as well as sub-groups based on size. These examinations supplement our investigation on firm TFP impulses from regional integration caused by new road constructions in subsection 5.2 and the corresponding baseline results given in Table 4.

In our baseline regressions, we applied a control variable based on terms of trade to account for adaptations to price developments. In Table B-1, we show the results, when this control variable is not applied. Although the point estimates in many cases are not too different when the control variable is excluded, there are some differences with regards to which industries face significant results. The regression results obtained after omitting the control variable suggest that firms within consumer manufacturing and wholesale and vehicle trade located close to major road openings have had a relatively beneficial productivity development compared to other firms along Southern Norway's coastline, but not when the study region is extended. In case of wholesale and vehicle trade, the placebo tests suggest that the results are influenced by underlying productivity trends. The results for information service firms are about the same as in the baseline regression with somewhat higher point estimates than when the terms of trade control is omitted. Yet, information service firms do under this specification seemingly pass the placebo test. The productivity impact estimates of increased market access for the tourism firms, when the study region is limited to Coastal Southern Norway, are no longer significant.

This is seemingly due to an underlying negative productive trend in firms located close to major road openings.

In our baseline regressions, we have pre-estimated TFP, before investigating market access' impulses on productivity. Such a two-step approach obviously involves an efficiency loss, as discussed briefly in subsection 2.3. However, the alternative one-step approach where market access is implicitly accounted for as a control in the production estimation involves other more severe challenges, such as lack of opportunities to account for industry-year dummies and to include observation unit fixed effects and cluster on standard errors on observation units due to computability challenges. In Table B-2, we depict the results of the alternative procedure with implicit estimation. Obviously, the impact and placebo impact estimates combined suggest that underlying industry trends affect the results substantially, when industry-year dummies are neglected. Under this approach, tourism firms seemingly receive productivity impulses from increased market access caused by expansion in the road network, both locally and when measured against a larger control region. Many other industries seemingly also receive impulses from regional integration, but these results appear to be caused by underlying trends with some exceptions when the extended study region is applied (e.g. negative for consumer manufacturing, and negative for technological manufacturing and business support). Another observation is that the impact estimation of increased market access is rather robust to the assumption on distance decay, when estimated implicit in the production estimation.

In line with our empirical investigation in subsection 5.1, we have applied agglomeration decay parameters $\delta^{pow} = 2.3$ and $\delta^{exp} = 0.07$ in case of a market access with power and exponential distance decay respectively. These estimates imply relatively sharp distance decay compared to other parameter values applied in the literature. In Table B-3, we have reported the regression results when the distance decay parameters instead are set to lower levels, more concretely $\delta^{pow} \in \{1.00, 1.65\}$ and $\delta^{exp} \in \{0.03, 0.05\}$. The tendencies are much of the same as in our baseline regression, but which results are significant is somewhat different. The results give some indications that consumer manufacturing and tourism firms close to new road constructions have had relatively beneficial productivity development after the corresponding road openings compared to the previous period, but only compared to other firms in the core study region. Some positive impact estimates are also produced for information services, but these results are not very stable and may also be caused by underlying development trends.

We now turn to productivity estimates produced by other production estimation approaches than Wooldridge's (2009) approach. In six of the approaches, we assume Cobb-Douglas (CD) technology, including regressions with ordinary least square (OLS) and linear panel data estimation with year and firm fixed effects (LFE) as neoclassical procedures, as well as the control function procedures of Olley and Pakes (1996; OP), Levinsohn and Petrin (2003; LP), Wooldridge (2009; W), Akerberg, Caves and Frazer (2015; ACF). In addition, we apply to assume constant elasticity of substitution (CES) technology for two procedures (confer Kmenta 1967), namely non-linear least squares (NLS) and linear panel data estimation with year and firm fixed, where the CES function is approximated through a Taylor expansion (based on Berndt and Christensen 1973). The neoclassical approaches to production estimation do not involve tools for handling selection biases, while the control function approaches applied beyond Wooldridge's procedure rely on two-step estimation, which turns out not to be compatible with selection correction for a large number of observations, when using the Stata command '*prodest*'. Consequently, we stick with lasting firms when considering productivity

impulses. The impact and placebo impact results are provided in Table B-4 to Table B-7, assuming power distance decay and exponential distance decay respectively.⁵

Our results on alternative estimation procedures suggest that the change of procedure influences the results to some degree, but the main patterns remain the same. For each pair of industry and market access measures, Wooldridge's estimation procedure tends to produce some of the either highest or lowest agglomeration elasticity estimates across the estimation approaches. For lasting firms, we seemingly find positive impacts of regional integration for consumer manufacturing, but the placebo test for our extended study region suggests that this appears to be related to underlying development trends. Underlying trends also appear to explain significant results for wholesale and vehicle trade, knowledge consultancy, business support services, where the results for knowledge consultancy and business support only are significant in application of the extended and narrow study regions respectively. Increased market access produces significant results for information services that pass the placebo test, when the narrow study region is applied. Wooldridge's estimation procedure constitutes the only approach that produces positive impact estimates for the tourism industry, but only for the narrow study region with estimates seeming unrealistically high. Otherwise, the placebo tests suggest negative underlying development trends in the core study region and positive underlying development trends in the extended study region.

Table B-8 and Table B-9 are related to our exploration on how firm productivity is affected differently across industries in small firms (defined as firms with average employment of less than ten from 2004 to 2008) and medium-sized and large firms (defined as firms with average employment of at least ten from 2004 to 2008) respectively. These years are chosen as they roughly can be considered as pretreatment years in our analysis, considering that most of the road construction between Kristiansand and Grimstad at European Route 18 was opened in 2009. For now, we limit ourselves to firms with at least one person engaged in each year of our study period, but we return to entry and exiting firms in subappendix B.3.

The productivity investigation on subsamples based on firm size reveals that the local productivity impulses in the tourism industry can be traced back to the small firms. Yet, these impulses are still not significant when the broader study region is applied. Similar results for small firms are also found for material manufacturing firms and wholesale and vehicle trade. The impulse estimates are also significant for business support, when the study region is limited to Coastal Southern Norway, but our placebo tests suggest that these are related to underlying development trends. For larger firms, the significant results were found for both wholesale and vehicle trade and information services, but the placebo tests suggest that underlying trends come into play.

As briefly discussed in subsection 2.3, technical productivity could increase even without improvements in factor productivity if the increase is unrelated to the factor technologies. Such improvements could take form as enhanced utilization of scale properties (i.e. scale efficiency) or prices' ability to reflect the underlying marginal costs and benefits (i.e. allocative

⁵ Due to space considerations, we have not included number of observations in these regressions tables on lasting firms, but these could be derived from Table B-8 and Table B-9.

efficiency).⁶ In Table B-10 and Table B-11, we have reported our regression results at firm level on impulses from increased market access caused by expansions in the road network on scale efficiency and allocative efficiency respectively. The results clearly suggest that there are no such efficiency improvements. The few significant results occurring do not pass their placebo tests.

Study region Industry \ distance decay	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	0.554** (0.244)	0.649** (0.297)	-0.003 (0.173)	0.038 (0.206)	-4.431*** (0.776)	-2.612*** (0.801)	0.197 (0.276)	0.199 (0.372)
Material manufacturing	1.273 (0.949)	0.746 (0.697)	-0.007 (0.130)	-0.127 (0.130)	0.197 (0.312)	0.235 (0.385)	-0.068 (0.216)	-0.065 (0.297)
Technological manufacturing	0.198 (0.190)	0.238 (0.295)	0.054 (0.144)	-0.132 (0.231)	1.226** (0.588)	2.749** (1.216)	0.101 (0.357)	-0.291 (0.789)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.317*** (0.112)	0.325** (0.149)	0.127** (0.052)	0.117** (0.057)	0.276 (0.241)	0.330 (0.370)	0.093 (0.075)	0.119 (0.109)
Retail trade	0.106 (0.245)	0.167 (0.288)	0.030 (0.086)	0.063 (0.083)	-0.131 (0.452)	-0.193 (0.720)	-0.019 (0.172)	-0.002 (0.195)
Transportation	0.117 (0.212)	0.058 (0.241)	0.051 (0.066)	0.041 (0.065)	0.939 (0.947)	0.800 (0.581)	0.073 (0.089)	0.094 (0.113)
Tourism	-0.185 (0.195)	-0.022 (0.318)	0.207 (0.172)	0.369** (0.162)	-1.135*** (0.385)	-1.595** (0.695)	0.298 (0.451)	0.553* (0.304)
Information services	0.397** (0.181)	0.660** (0.278)	0.117* (0.063)	0.124* (0.070)	-0.123 (0.256)	-0.183 (0.288)	0.111 (0.139)	0.161* (0.089)
Knowledge consultancy	0.233 (0.153)	0.140 (0.129)	0.047 (0.052)	0.025 (0.055)	0.264 (0.656)	0.168 (0.694)	0.106 (0.079)	0.090 (0.073)
Business support	0.011 (0.313)	0.078 (0.346)	0.092 (0.125)	0.128 (0.112)	0.668 (0.623)	1.488* (0.791)	0.216 (0.219)	0.331 (0.215)

Table B-1: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure without terms of trade as control variable and correction for firm exits. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

⁶ Growth in scale efficiency, \dot{s} , is approximated as $\dot{s} = (\alpha_K - \alpha_L - 1) \left(\frac{\alpha_K k + \alpha_L l}{\alpha_K + \alpha_L} \right)$, while growth in allocative efficiency, \dot{a} , is approximated as $\dot{a} = \left(\frac{\alpha_K}{\alpha_K + \alpha_L} - \frac{r}{r+w} \right) \dot{k} + \left(\frac{\alpha_L}{\alpha_K + \alpha_L} - \frac{w}{r+w} \right) \dot{l}$. Here, l and k are natural logarithms of labor and fixed capital with corresponding factor elasticities α_K and α_L and factor returns w and r , respectively.

Impact on TFP Study region Industry \ distance decay	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	-0.939*** (0.238)	-0.935*** (0.235)	1.780*** (0.516)	1.738*** (0.522)	-0.447*** (0.127)	-0.430*** (0.129)	-0.037 (0.368)	0.018 (0.375)
Material manufacturing	-0.807*** (0.139)	-0.806*** (0.150)	-0.637*** (0.220)	-0.638*** (0.222)	-0.683*** (0.094)	-0.676*** (0.093)	-0.747*** (0.088)	-0.747*** (0.087)
Technological manufacturing	-0.458* (0.254)	-0.451* (0.254)	-1.365** (0.538)	-1.360** (0.541)	-0.328** (0.135)	-0.310** (0.134)	-0.300 (0.211)	-0.290 (0.210)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	-0.397*** (0.143)	-0.395*** (0.144)	-0.109 (0.449)	-0.086 (0.459)	-0.206*** (0.067)	-0.212*** (0.067)	0.171 (0.159)	0.169 (0.160)
Retail trade	-0.194 (0.319)	-0.187 (0.320)	0.224 (0.233)	0.208 (0.230)	-0.267** (0.113)	-0.279** (0.112)	-0.468* (0.273)	-0.467* (0.274)
Transportation	0.100 (0.228)	0.072 (0.227)	0.267 (0.233)	0.265 (0.234)	-0.132 (0.134)	-0.116 (0.134)	-0.050 (0.176)	-0.024 (0.175)
Tourism	0.757** (0.353)	0.766** (0.354)	1.035*** (0.201)	1.031*** (0.200)	0.199 (0.243)	0.208 (0.243)	0.507 (0.322)	0.496 (0.319)
Information services	-0.321*** (0.114)	-0.318*** (0.112)	-0.281* (0.160)	-0.283* (0.160)	-0.175** (0.068)	-0.174** (0.068)	-0.070 (0.104)	-0.074 (0.104)
Knowledge consultancy	-0.383*** (0.089)	-0.387*** (0.089)	-0.396** (0.158)	-0.383** (0.159)	-0.411*** (0.047)	-0.413*** (0.048)	-0.401*** (0.080)	-0.400*** (0.080)
Business support	-0.668*** (0.223)	-0.664*** (0.222)	-0.409 (0.454)	-0.400 (0.448)	-0.328*** (0.088)	-0.339*** (0.088)	-0.261** (0.120)	-0.261** (0.120)

**Table B-2: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at firm level, estimated by implicitly as a control variable in the estimation of the production function. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for firm exits as an additional control.
(* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and *** for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP Industry \ Study region		Impact				Placebo			
		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Power decay		$\delta = 1$	$\delta = 1.65$	$\delta = 1$	$\delta = 1.65$	$\delta = 1$	$\delta = 1.65$	$\delta = 1$	$\delta = 1.65$
Consumer manufacturing		5.460** (2.715)	1.401 (0.881)	-1.293 (1.585)	-0.154 (0.521)	-19.34** (7.846)	-9.881** (3.835)	0.799 (1.844)	0.267 (0.561)
Material manufacturing		13.13* (7.582)	3.032 (2.155)	0.195 (0.583)	0.005 (0.200)	6.767* (4.072)	0.955 (0.848)	-0.887 (2.051)	-0.252 (0.453)
Technological manufacturing		2.270 (4.555)	0.837 (0.905)	8.571 (9.065)	2.453 (2.349)	20.13*** (6.116)	3.646*** (1.072)	9.124 (11.280)	1.107 (1.223)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		12.990 (7.946)	2.275 (1.417)	0.288 (0.587)	0.081 (0.207)	1.248 (3.972)	0.575 (0.542)	-0.022 (0.480)	0.111 (0.124)
Retail trade		5.646 (3.955)	0.297 (0.662)	0.853 (1.690)	0.192 (0.318)	-20.080 (17.250)	-2.233 (2.729)	-9.995 (8.035)	-1.706 (1.759)
Transportation		-23.250 (28.630)	-0.936 (2.500)	-0.499 (0.697)	-0.018 (0.162)	49.180 (30.130)	9.108 (5.963)	0.155 (1.488)	-0.039 (0.368)
Tourism		85.460 (53.230)	21.96* (11.490)	-1.625 (25.480)	1.737 (8.965)	-8.027** (3.491)	-2.208*** (0.816)	2.208 (2.425)	1.190 (1.098)
Information services		2.929 (1.833)	0.667* (0.376)	0.870* (0.500)	0.197 (0.125)	-0.285 (1.668)	-0.251 (0.468)	0.333 (0.934)	0.123 (0.266)
Knowledge consultancy		1.716 (2.861)	0.513 (0.570)	0.640 (0.641)	0.248 (0.170)	2.002 (7.707)	0.520 (1.456)	0.614 (0.864)	0.162 (0.209)
Business support		3.829 (3.400)	-0.122 (0.762)	3.688 (3.832)	1.225 (1.215)	19.800 (17.370)	1.894 (1.735)	1.242 (1.292)	0.295 (0.405)
Exponential decay		$\delta = 0.03$	$\delta = 0.05$	$\delta = 0.03$	$\delta = 0.05$	$\delta = 0.03$	$\delta = 0.05$	$\delta = 0.03$	$\delta = 0.05$
Consumer manufacturing		1.285 (0.949)	1.057 (0.735)	-0.097 (0.732)	0.086 (0.472)	-3.183*** (0.876)	-3.003*** (1.068)	0.683 (1.081)	0.247 (0.619)
Material manufacturing		0.935 (1.122)	0.730 (0.794)	-0.178 (0.186)	-0.166 (0.150)	1.105 (0.946)	0.429 (0.536)	-0.951 (1.017)	-0.475 (0.530)
Technological manufacturing		0.819 (1.153)	0.857 (0.693)	1.520 (2.196)	1.085 (1.406)	7.390*** (2.598)	4.716*** (1.424)	1.610 (1.752)	0.483 (1.381)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		3.535 (2.412)	1.979 (1.447)	0.171 (0.191)	0.099 (0.137)	0.281 (1.305)	0.346 (0.586)	0.115 (0.221)	0.117 (0.140)
Retail trade		0.999* (0.578)	-0.170 (0.827)	0.148 (0.383)	0.068 (0.262)	1.588 (4.003)	1.473 (2.796)	-2.196 (2.955)	-1.576 (2.178)
Transportation		-1.001 (3.510)	-0.102 (1.379)	0.009 (0.191)	0.056 (0.124)	7.310 (4.683)	3.721 (2.357)	0.046 (0.402)	0.043 (0.274)
Tourism		40.45*** (15.360)	26.57*** (9.419)	-4.426 (13.240)	-0.731 (5.398)	-3.067** (1.377)	-1.946** (0.883)	2.349*** (0.818)	1.359*** (0.439)
Information services		1.036 (0.718)	0.743* (0.411)	0.191 (0.141)	0.148* (0.090)	-0.421 (0.586)	-0.344 (0.405)	0.220 (0.236)	0.186* (0.109)
Knowledge consultancy		0.334 (0.647)	0.180 (0.351)	0.054 (0.232)	0.061 (0.135)	-0.230 (1.424)	0.049 (0.851)	0.256 (0.226)	0.135 (0.124)
Business support		1.467 (1.346)	0.287 (0.584)	0.445 (0.366)	0.335 (0.281)	6.006* (3.242)	2.463* (1.316)	0.322 (0.236)	0.311 (0.220)

Table B-3: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} \in \{1, 1.65\}$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} \in \{0.03, 0.05\}$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for firm exits. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP		Power distance decay						
Industry \ prod. est. proc.	OLS, CD	LFE, CD	OP, CD	ACF, CD	LP, CD	W, CD	NLS, CES	LFE, CES
Core study region								
Consumer manufacturing	0.514** (0.249)	0.545** (0.240)	0.523** (0.247)	0.513** (0.251)	0.561** (0.256)	0.581* (0.301)	0.574** (0.250)	0.516** (0.240)
Material manufacturing	0.948 (1.025)	1.289 (0.953)	0.941 (1.024)	0.959 (1.023)	1.247 (0.952)	0.920 (1.173)	1.012 (0.997)	1.368 (0.950)
Technological manufacturing	0.243 (0.208)	0.212 (0.193)	0.246 (0.209)	0.235 (0.203)	0.221 (0.195)	0.437 (0.411)	0.225 (0.204)	0.218 (0.193)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.172 (0.118)	0.319*** (0.112)	0.157 (0.117)	0.179 (0.117)	0.247** (0.124)	2.629 (2.124)	0.197* (0.111)	0.311*** (0.109)
Retail trade	0.096 (0.252)	0.104 (0.245)	0.097 (0.250)	0.087 (0.258)	0.112 (0.241)	0.007 (0.763)	0.051 (0.273)	0.102 (0.241)
Transportation	0.144 (0.170)	0.118 (0.212)	0.139 (0.176)	0.151 (0.164)	0.126 (0.202)	0.116 (0.700)	0.102 (0.175)	0.124 (0.213)
Tourism	0.013 (0.237)	-0.196 (0.196)	-0.013 (0.229)	-0.521* (0.283)	-0.131 (0.198)	15.56* (8.167)	0.115 (0.255)	-0.192 (0.196)
Information services	0.269 (0.198)	0.445** (0.177)	0.287 (0.195)	0.278 (0.197)	0.384** (0.179)	0.250 (0.199)	0.314* (0.186)	0.435** (0.177)
Knowledge consultancy	0.182 (0.140)	0.243 (0.156)	0.186 (0.140)	0.182 (0.140)	0.225 (0.150)	0.220 (0.237)	0.198 (0.143)	0.243 (0.156)
Business support	0.019 (0.310)	0.032 (0.320)	0.031 (0.312)	0.030 (0.311)	0.023 (0.316)	-0.177 (0.397)	-0.013 (0.310)	0.041 (0.316)
Extended study region								
Consumer manufacturing	0.171* (0.101)	0.170* (0.094)	0.171* (0.099)	0.174* (0.101)	0.180* (0.095)	0.066 (0.158)	0.166 (0.101)	0.175* (0.097)
Material manufacturing	-0.065 (0.102)	-0.064 (0.103)	-0.068 (0.104)	-0.065 (0.102)	-0.071 (0.106)	-0.059 (0.291)	-0.062 (0.102)	-0.056 (0.104)
Technological manufacturing	0.109 (0.079)	0.079 (0.076)	0.107 (0.079)	0.115 (0.080)	0.092 (0.077)	2.229 (1.417)	0.107 (0.079)	0.077 (0.076)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.015 (0.043)	0.053 (0.044)	0.013 (0.044)	0.016 (0.043)	0.045 (0.047)	0.292 (0.526)	0.019 (0.044)	0.055 (0.044)
Retail trade	-0.071 (0.096)	-0.053 (0.096)	-0.067 (0.096)	-0.059 (0.101)	-0.050 (0.094)	0.144 (0.348)	-0.073 (0.095)	-0.065 (0.096)
Transportation	0.061 (0.055)	0.084 (0.056)	0.061 (0.055)	0.061 (0.056)	0.075 (0.056)	0.802 (0.736)	0.062 (0.057)	0.086 (0.057)
Tourism	-0.030 (0.125)	0.025 (0.122)	-0.024 (0.124)	0.149 (0.177)	0.002 (0.119)	-5.227 (4.074)	-0.028 (0.131)	0.027 (0.122)
Information services	-0.043 (0.062)	0.020 (0.063)	-0.037 (0.062)	-0.037 (0.063)	-0.003 (0.062)	-0.010 (0.070)	-0.029 (0.062)	0.023 (0.063)
Knowledge consultancy	0.077* (0.040)	0.102** (0.041)	0.078* (0.040)	0.077* (0.040)	0.093** (0.041)	0.148* (0.090)	0.080** (0.040)	0.102** (0.042)
Business support	0.186* (0.111)	0.194* (0.108)	0.141 (0.122)	0.110 (0.136)	0.070 (0.161)	1.635 (1.370)	0.180 (0.110)	0.194* (0.108)

Table B-4: Impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP in lasting firms over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with exponential distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$). Procedures for production estimation and production technologies are indicated in the table. Production estimation is carried out with terms of trade as control variable. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP		Power distance decay						
Industry \ prod. est. proc.	OLS, CD	LFE, CD	OP, CD	ACF, CD	LP, CD	W, CD	NLS, CES	LFE, CES
Core study region								
Consumer manufacturing	-4.782*** (0.820)	-4.515*** (0.775)	-4.709*** (0.809)	-4.762*** (0.829)	-4.303*** (0.789)	-5.376*** (0.797)	-4.338*** (0.821)	-4.459*** (0.780)
Material manufacturing	-0.484 (0.685)	0.337 (0.324)	-0.548 (0.668)	-0.460 (0.677)	0.108 (0.317)	0.300 (0.311)	-0.322 (0.613)	0.524* (0.310)
Technological manufacturing	1.223** (0.588)	1.261** (0.577)	1.236** (0.584)	1.204** (0.594)	1.286** (0.570)	1.476*** (0.492)	1.242** (0.594)	1.219** (0.585)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.285 (0.320)	0.274 (0.240)	0.276 (0.317)	0.285 (0.321)	0.279 (0.245)	0.315 (0.224)	0.287 (0.302)	0.266 (0.235)
Retail trade	-0.199 (0.461)	-0.136 (0.453)	-0.188 (0.463)	-0.192 (0.581)	-0.166 (0.450)	-0.050 (2.610)	-0.256 (0.518)	-0.150 (0.460)
Transportation	0.423 (0.681)	0.961 (0.952)	0.487 (0.724)	0.372 (0.649)	0.837 (0.911)	4.243 (2.856)	0.439 (0.656)	0.985 (0.938)
Tourism	-1.275*** (0.394)	-1.145*** (0.377)	-1.256*** (0.395)	-1.290*** (0.387)	-1.134*** (0.405)	-1.092*** (0.363)	-1.209*** (0.449)	-1.140*** (0.376)
Information services	-0.352 (0.311)	-0.040 (0.252)	-0.325 (0.303)	-0.332 (0.305)	-0.152 (0.263)	-0.212 (0.272)	-0.239 (0.286)	-0.027 (0.248)
Knowledge consultancy	0.280 (0.616)	0.260 (0.665)	0.283 (0.616)	0.273 (0.619)	0.277 (0.643)	0.228 (0.656)	0.271 (0.623)	0.257 (0.663)
Business support	0.622 (0.642)	0.700 (0.615)	0.625 (0.642)	0.619 (0.643)	0.667 (0.623)	0.672 (0.626)	0.632 (0.642)	0.720 (0.611)
Extended study region								
Consumer manufacturing	0.258* (0.138)	0.205 (0.138)	0.249* (0.137)	0.263* (0.138)	0.220 (0.135)	0.170 (0.145)	0.236* (0.131)	0.204 (0.135)
Material manufacturing	-0.172* (0.101)	-0.154 (0.103)	-0.170* (0.101)	-0.172* (0.101)	-0.151 (0.103)	-0.127 (0.603)	-0.159 (0.102)	-0.152 (0.103)
Technological manufacturing	0.031 (0.154)	0.060 (0.148)	0.035 (0.153)	0.026 (0.155)	0.067 (0.146)	0.020 (0.229)	0.017 (0.152)	0.060 (0.149)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	-0.010 (0.087)	0.021 (0.083)	-0.010 (0.086)	-0.010 (0.087)	0.020 (0.083)	0.016 (0.086)	0.010 (0.082)	0.026 (0.082)
Retail trade	-0.260 (0.189)	-0.188 (0.177)	-0.256 (0.189)	-0.487 (0.346)	-0.202 (0.175)	-3.258 (3.125)	-0.254 (0.185)	-0.193 (0.180)
Transportation	0.037 (0.076)	0.068 (0.077)	0.041 (0.076)	0.033 (0.076)	0.063 (0.076)	-0.022 (0.127)	0.034 (0.084)	0.060 (0.078)
Tourism	0.404 (0.319)	0.554* (0.295)	0.416 (0.313)	0.399 (0.323)	0.505* (0.283)	0.854* (0.440)	0.382 (0.343)	0.552* (0.294)
Information services	-0.082 (0.094)	-0.003 (0.088)	-0.076 (0.093)	-0.074 (0.094)	-0.033 (0.090)	-0.013 (0.095)	-0.059 (0.091)	-0.002 (0.088)
Knowledge consultancy	0.079 (0.060)	0.113* (0.061)	0.079 (0.060)	0.080 (0.060)	0.100* (0.060)	0.072 (0.073)	0.083 (0.060)	0.115* (0.061)
Business support	0.168 (0.153)	0.111 (0.141)	0.175 (0.154)	0.174 (0.154)	0.111 (0.140)	0.093 (0.147)	0.161 (0.150)	0.109 (0.141)

Table B-5: Placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP in lasting firms over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with exponential distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$). Procedures for production estimation and production technologies are indicated in the table. Production estimation is carried out with terms of trade as control variable. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP		Exponential distance decay						
Industry \ prod. est. proc.	OLS, CD	LFE, CD	OP, CD	ACF, CD	LP, CD	W, CD	NLS, CES	LFE, CES
Core study region								
Consumer manufacturing	0.652** (0.307)	0.639** (0.295)	0.659** (0.304)	0.657** (0.310)	0.698** (0.306)	0.751** (0.375)	0.652** (0.319)	0.607** (0.284)
Material manufacturing	0.314 (0.741)	0.770 (0.710)	0.306 (0.737)	0.326 (0.740)	0.713 (0.694)	0.604 (1.027)	0.449 (0.698)	0.854 (0.718)
Technological manufacturing	0.362 (0.324)	0.260 (0.298)	0.365 (0.325)	0.349 (0.317)	0.271 (0.299)	0.654 (0.540)	0.323 (0.317)	0.261 (0.297)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.145 (0.173)	0.328** (0.148)	0.122 (0.175)	0.157 (0.173)	0.204 (0.182)	4.384 (3.816)	0.186 (0.162)	0.320** (0.145)
Retail trade	0.156 (0.293)	0.165 (0.289)	0.152 (0.293)	0.029 (0.362)	0.172 (0.283)	-1.540 (2.470)	0.112 (0.314)	0.154 (0.283)
Transportation	0.099 (0.180)	0.059 (0.241)	0.092 (0.189)	0.106 (0.172)	0.069 (0.227)	0.039 (0.891)	0.062 (0.187)	0.072 (0.243)
Tourism	0.300 (0.320)	-0.043 (0.321)	0.258 (0.316)	-0.626 (0.404)	0.073 (0.310)	27.19*** (10.200)	0.461 (0.323)	-0.036 (0.321)
Information services	0.594** (0.301)	0.690** (0.275)	0.605** (0.296)	0.595** (0.299)	0.658** (0.276)	0.492 (0.304)	0.610** (0.289)	0.679** (0.275)
Knowledge consultancy	0.109 (0.120)	0.145 (0.131)	0.113 (0.121)	0.105 (0.120)	0.141 (0.128)	0.127 (0.252)	0.126 (0.125)	0.144 (0.132)
Business support	0.086 (0.358)	0.092 (0.352)	0.092 (0.360)	0.090 (0.358)	0.079 (0.344)	0.029 (0.444)	0.067 (0.346)	0.106 (0.347)
Extended study region								
Consumer manufacturing	0.177 (0.111)	0.171 (0.108)	0.177 (0.109)	0.180 (0.111)	0.186* (0.104)	0.075 (0.162)	0.169 (0.114)	0.175 (0.111)
Material manufacturing	-0.138 (0.102)	-0.134 (0.102)	-0.140 (0.104)	-0.139 (0.101)	-0.140 (0.106)	-0.041 (0.293)	-0.133 (0.102)	-0.129 (0.103)
Technological manufacturing	0.070 (0.069)	0.045 (0.063)	0.067 (0.068)	0.076 (0.070)	0.060 (0.066)	2.539* (1.511)	0.071 (0.067)	0.042 (0.063)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	-0.002 (0.046)	0.041 (0.047)	-0.002 (0.047)	-0.002 (0.046)	0.036 (0.049)	0.135 (0.382)	0.002 (0.046)	0.043 (0.047)
Retail trade	-0.108 (0.098)	-0.073 (0.097)	-0.101 (0.098)	-0.100 (0.107)	-0.074 (0.095)	0.076 (0.381)	-0.109 (0.095)	-0.083 (0.097)
Transportation	0.048 (0.051)	0.063 (0.051)	0.048 (0.051)	0.047 (0.052)	0.057 (0.051)	0.569 (0.500)	0.055 (0.052)	0.068 (0.052)
Tourism	-0.041 (0.147)	0.002 (0.142)	-0.037 (0.146)	0.182 (0.215)	-0.028 (0.141)	-6.451 (4.848)	-0.027 (0.150)	0.004 (0.141)
Information services	-0.024 (0.061)	0.033 (0.062)	-0.019 (0.061)	-0.019 (0.061)	0.012 (0.060)	0.003 (0.066)	-0.011 (0.061)	0.036 (0.062)
Knowledge consultancy	0.069 (0.045)	0.089* (0.046)	0.070 (0.045)	0.070 (0.045)	0.082* (0.045)	0.148* (0.087)	0.072 (0.045)	0.089* (0.046)
Business support	0.202* (0.103)	0.211** (0.102)	0.173 (0.110)	0.153 (0.118)	0.130 (0.134)	1.145 (0.995)	0.199* (0.102)	0.213** (0.102)

Table B-6: Impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP in lasting firms over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). Procedures for production estimation and production technologies are indicated in the table. Production estimation is carried out with terms of trade as control variable. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP		Exponential distance decay						
Industry \ prod. est. proc.	OLS, CD	LFE, CD	OP, CD	ACF, CD	LP, CD	W, CD	NLS, CES	LFE, CES
Core study region								
Consumer manufacturing	-2.771*** (0.910)	-2.645*** (0.821)	-2.740*** (0.890)	-2.767*** (0.908)	-2.583*** (0.790)	-2.945*** (1.062)	-2.658*** (0.794)	-2.616*** (0.833)
Material manufacturing	-0.754 (0.704)	0.397 (0.401)	-0.826 (0.684)	-0.720 (0.698)	0.122 (0.387)	0.192 (0.387)	-0.513 (0.657)	0.646* (0.384)
Technological manufacturing	2.736** (1.227)	2.794** (1.191)	2.753** (1.218)	2.712** (1.240)	2.827** (1.174)	3.097*** (1.007)	2.767** (1.228)	2.731** (1.206)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.342 (0.503)	0.327 (0.368)	0.330 (0.497)	0.342 (0.503)	0.336 (0.378)	0.362 (0.361)	0.348 (0.472)	0.319 (0.362)
Retail trade	-0.304 (0.727)	-0.200 (0.720)	-0.275 (0.734)	-0.055 (0.955)	-0.259 (0.723)	3.159 (5.124)	-0.351 (0.792)	-0.210 (0.730)
Transportation	0.507 (0.383)	0.809 (0.590)	0.543 (0.404)	0.473 (0.370)	0.733 (0.552)	2.984 (1.932)	0.475 (0.358)	0.828 (0.577)
Tourism	-1.744** (0.680)	-1.610** (0.682)	-1.722** (0.685)	-1.768*** (0.671)	-1.584** (0.720)	-1.425** (0.625)	-1.591** (0.710)	-1.604** (0.681)
Information services	-0.453 (0.415)	-0.082 (0.271)	-0.421 (0.397)	-0.433 (0.403)	-0.213 (0.302)	-0.304 (0.343)	-0.292 (0.337)	-0.063 (0.266)
Knowledge consultancy	0.218 (0.655)	0.156 (0.704)	0.222 (0.655)	0.207 (0.658)	0.194 (0.680)	0.129 (0.696)	0.202 (0.659)	0.149 (0.701)
Business support	1.424* (0.818)	1.528* (0.775)	1.426* (0.817)	1.419* (0.820)	1.487* (0.791)	1.502* (0.791)	1.441* (0.820)	1.550** (0.770)
Extended study region								
Consumer manufacturing	0.347** (0.172)	0.295* (0.175)	0.337** (0.172)	0.352** (0.171)	0.307* (0.169)	0.259 (0.186)	0.314* (0.162)	0.291* (0.169)
Material manufacturing	-0.180* (0.095)	-0.154 (0.102)	-0.177* (0.096)	-0.184* (0.094)	-0.148 (0.103)	0.303 (0.870)	-0.167* (0.097)	-0.152 (0.101)
Technological manufacturing	0.053 (0.241)	0.108 (0.223)	0.058 (0.239)	0.050 (0.241)	0.116 (0.222)	0.220 (0.415)	0.049 (0.235)	0.109 (0.224)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.023 (0.094)	0.055 (0.091)	0.023 (0.093)	0.023 (0.094)	0.053 (0.091)	0.050 (0.093)	0.042 (0.091)	0.059 (0.090)
Retail trade	-0.267 (0.186)	-0.220 (0.173)	-0.272 (0.185)	-0.587 (0.370)	-0.230 (0.171)	-4.584 (3.739)	-0.253 (0.182)	-0.226 (0.176)
Transportation	0.059 (0.079)	0.078 (0.080)	0.062 (0.079)	0.058 (0.078)	0.075 (0.079)	0.003 (0.107)	0.065 (0.086)	0.071 (0.080)
Tourism	0.515 (0.437)	0.806** (0.407)	0.539 (0.431)	0.500 (0.443)	0.713* (0.393)	1.510 (0.974)	0.476 (0.472)	0.802** (0.407)
Information services	-0.071 (0.080)	-0.003 (0.075)	-0.065 (0.080)	-0.064 (0.080)	-0.029 (0.076)	-0.011 (0.081)	-0.053 (0.078)	-0.003 (0.075)
Knowledge consultancy	0.102 (0.066)	0.134** (0.066)	0.102 (0.065)	0.104 (0.066)	0.121* (0.065)	0.111 (0.072)	0.106 (0.065)	0.136** (0.067)
Business support	0.273* (0.148)	0.220* (0.123)	0.278* (0.152)	0.278* (0.151)	0.223* (0.122)	0.204 (0.128)	0.267* (0.148)	0.219* (0.123)

Table B-7: Placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP in lasting firms over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). Procedures for production estimation and production technologies are indicated in the table. Production estimation is carried out with terms of trade as control variable. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP Firm size Industry \ distance key	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	0.286	-0.025	0.424	0.340	-4.693	-2.153**	-0.510	-1.328*
	(0.983)	(0.893)	(0.653)	(0.437)	(4.356)	(0.984)	(0.681)	(0.678)
	n = 434	n = 434	n = 1,937	n = 1,937	n = 198	n = 198	n = 924	n = 924
Material manufacturing	3.752***	3.847**	0.059	-0.066	1.234	1.189	-0.072	-0.465
	(1.165)	(1.780)	(0.215)	(0.253)	(1.999)	(3.118)	(0.261)	(0.898)
	n = 459	n = 459	n = 2,429	n = 2,429	n = 221	n = 221	n = 1,189	n = 1,189
Technological manufacturing	-9.491	-7.199	2.923	3.201	0.467	-1.917	0.926	2.649
	(8.241)	(5.269)	(3.074)	(3.651)	(1.166)	(2.775)	(1.201)	(2.812)
	n = 289	n = 289	n = 1,488	n = 1,488	n = 137	n = 137	n = 708	n = 708
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.610**	0.730**	-0.021	-0.015	0.199	0.279	0.067	0.032
	(0.256)	(0.331)	(0.164)	(0.153)	(0.352)	(0.475)	(0.118)	(0.120)
	n = 1,596	n = 1,596	n = 7,974	n = 7,974	n = 761	n = 761	n = 3,883	n = 3,883
Retail trade	-0.371	-2.323	-0.092	-0.368	-0.450	0.836	-1.640	-3.216
	(0.581)	(2.595)	(0.276)	(0.672)	(1.680)	(3.211)	(2.015)	(4.300)
	n = 2,259	n = 2,259	n = 8,942	n = 8,942	n = 998	n = 998	n = 4,336	n = 4,336
Transportation	0.588	0.789	0.100	0.168	15.47***	15.02***	-0.043	0.069
	(0.374)	(0.546)	(0.135)	(0.130)	(5.269)	(3.237)	(0.451)	(0.533)
	n = 586	n = 586	n = 3,506	n = 3,506	n = 258	n = 258	n = 1,628	n = 1,628
Tourism	13.40***	19.21***	-4.584	-11.690	-0.826**	-1.022**	-0.797***	-0.974**
	(3.903)	(3.557)	(15.280)	(28.700)	(0.342)	(0.460)	(0.295)	(0.441)
	n = 362	n = 362	n = 2,112	n = 2,112	n = 153	n = 153	n = 984	n = 984
Information services	-0.044	0.491	0.141	0.142	-0.183	-0.269	0.002	0.089
	(0.617)	(0.634)	(0.099)	(0.089)	(0.156)	(0.188)	(0.184)	(0.111)
	n = 482	n = 482	n = 2,314	n = 2,314	n = 220	n = 220	n = 1,095	n = 1,095
Knowledge consultancy	0.150	0.078	0.009	-0.128	0.710	0.542	0.029	0.052
	(0.278)	(0.271)	(0.147)	(0.155)	(0.922)	(0.856)	(0.181)	(0.125)
	n = 2,090	n = 2,090	n = 7,843	n = 7,843	n = 915	n = 915	n = 3,639	n = 3,639
Business support	0.745***	1.564**	0.024	0.092	4.236	13.610	0.111	0.186
	(0.249)	(0.726)	(0.246)	(0.191)	(5.539)	(9.465)	(0.289)	(0.161)
	n = 312	n = 312	n = 1,626	n = 1,626	n = 138	n = 138	n = 767	n = 767

Table B-8: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Limited to lasting firms with average employment of at least 10 employees from 2004 to 2008. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for firm exits. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP Firm size Industry \ distance key	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	8.848	6.815	2.323	3.254	25.25***	24.44***	3.923***	5.269***
	(7.569)	(4.946)	(1.514)	(2.375)	(8.223)	(8.299)	(1.103)	(0.832)
	n = 233	n = 233	n = 1,015	n = 1,015	n = 98	n = 98	n = 476	n = 476
Material manufacturing	1.403	1.364	-0.041	-0.030	-5.549	-3.870	-0.147	-0.203
	(3.557)	(2.092)	(0.191)	(0.298)	(11.480)	(6.783)	(0.107)	(0.216)
	n = 292	n = 292	n = 1,334	n = 1,334	n = 137	n = 137	n = 645	n = 645
Technological manufacturing	0.091	0.074	-0.340	-0.587	17.58*	29.06**	-0.976	-2.003*
	(0.413)	(0.580)	(0.355)	(0.570)	(9.857)	(13.440)	(0.636)	(1.018)
	n = 150	n = 150	n = 674	n = 674	n = 65	n = 65	n = 320	n = 320
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.988*	1.049	0.047	0.095	0.927	3.059*	0.114	0.415
	(0.574)	(0.639)	(0.117)	(0.131)	(0.973)	(1.605)	(0.175)	(0.336)
	n = 451	n = 451	n = 1,718	n = 1,718	n = 194	n = 194	n = 814	n = 814
Retail trade	0.787***	0.579***	0.324	0.540	1.710	2.241	3.574	3.401
	(0.202)	(0.128)	(0.445)	(0.328)	(4.865)	(4.501)	(3.446)	(2.709)
	n = 537	n = 537	n = 2,698	n = 2,698	n = 237	n = 237	n = 1,263	n = 1,263
Transportation	2.525	3.657	0.017	-0.051	-0.406	2.201	-0.013	-0.170
	(2.663)	(2.280)	(0.084)	(0.112)	(7.980)	(9.521)	(0.104)	(0.181)
	n = 175	n = 175	n = 941	n = 941	n = 85	n = 85	n = 436	n = 436
Tourism	-7.114	-2.188	-1.061	-3.945	-15.310	-8.460	4.145**	3.032*
	(8.251)	(3.731)	(2.936)	(7.030)	(11.190)	(11.370)	(1.911)	(1.556)
	n = 352	n = 352	n = 1,601	n = 1,601	n = 151	n = 151	n = 738	n = 738
Information services	0.331**	0.348	0.179***	0.156***	1.985**	8.978**	1.556***	1.883***
	(0.116)	(0.227)	(0.059)	(0.041)	(0.703)	(3.632)	(0.443)	(0.586)
	n = 110	n = 110	n = 685	n = 685	n = 47	n = 47	n = 302	n = 302
Knowledge consultancy	-1.039	-1.041	0.038	-0.479	-11.030	-12.780	-0.319	-0.369
	(3.605)	(2.608)	(0.270)	(0.510)	(8.214)	(8.595)	(0.225)	(0.294)
	n = 155	n = 155	n = 844	n = 844	n = 72	n = 72	n = 393	n = 393
Business support	-0.377	-0.101	0.103	0.233	-5.655	-13.140	-1.189	-1.043
	(0.368)	(1.411)	(0.304)	(0.399)	(8.222)	(13.250)	(1.100)	(1.524)
	n = 87	n = 87	n = 630	n = 630	n = 40	n = 40	n = 289	n = 289

Table B-9: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Limited to lasting firms with average employment of at least 10 employees from 2004 to 2008. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for firm exits. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on scale efficiency		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region		Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing		0.129 (0.132)	0.054 (0.088)	0.036 (0.033)	0.028 (0.031)	0.228 (0.347)	0.019 (0.075)	0.072*** (0.026)	0.086*** (0.022)
Material manufacturing		0.053 (0.181)	0.006 (0.144)	-0.004 (0.028)	-0.011 (0.031)	0.465 (0.282)	0.541 (0.511)	-0.025 (0.032)	-0.049* (0.029)
Technological manufacturing		0.009 (0.020)	0.020 (0.033)	0.030 (0.022)	0.042 (0.029)	0.048 (0.156)	0.245 (0.381)	0.044 (0.047)	0.027 (0.064)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		0.011 (0.135)	0.074 (0.128)	0.018 (0.027)	0.045 (0.044)	0.108 (0.108)	0.167 (0.125)	0.018 (0.035)	0.043 (0.053)
Retail trade		-0.075 (0.183)	-0.040 (0.222)	-0.086 (0.056)	-0.089* (0.047)	-0.125 (0.132)	-0.166 (0.199)	-0.096* (0.056)	-0.100 (0.063)
Transportation		-0.117** (0.059)	-0.114 (0.092)	-0.037*** (0.014)	-0.029* (0.016)	-0.457** (0.199)	-0.249 (0.194)	-0.033 (0.022)	-0.032 (0.029)
Tourism		-0.030 (0.065)	0.017 (0.187)	-0.006 (0.049)	0.064 (0.077)	-0.057 (0.073)	0.002 (0.259)	-0.085 (0.080)	-0.357* (0.207)
Information services		0.039 (0.035)	0.077 (0.063)	0.009 (0.006)	0.011** (0.005)	0.005 (0.021)	0.007 (0.023)	-0.016 (0.024)	-0.023 (0.031)
Knowledge consultancy		-0.055 (0.035)	-0.003 (0.046)	-0.013 (0.015)	0.009 (0.016)	-0.022 (0.045)	-0.012 (0.054)	-0.019* (0.011)	-0.006 (0.018)
Business support		0.020 (0.062)	0.040 (0.091)	0.012 (0.015)	0.011 (0.012)	0.167 (0.205)	0.066 (0.418)	0.017 (0.022)	0.014 (0.025)

Table B-10: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on scale efficiency over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for firm exits. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on allocative eff. Distance decay Industry \ Study region	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	1.628 (1.780)	0.764 (1.843)	3.060 (3.254)	2.612 (2.702)	2.720 (4.292)	-0.111 (0.350)	0.184 (0.112)	0.199 (0.132)
Material manufacturing	-2.556 (2.233)	-4.397 (3.382)	-0.132 (0.235)	-0.453 (0.408)	1.490 (2.169)	6.660 (7.894)	0.012 (0.090)	0.019 (0.137)
Technological manufacturing	-0.141* (0.075)	-0.161* (0.094)	0.006 (0.072)	0.008 (0.065)	-0.359 (0.452)	-0.640 (0.760)	2.032 (2.430)	3.003 (3.271)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	-0.023 (0.084)	-0.019 (0.089)	0.014 (0.052)	0.000 (0.054)	-0.098 (0.063)	-0.118 (0.095)	-0.073** (0.033)	-0.092*** (0.035)
Retail trade	-0.113 (0.095)	-0.411 (0.338)	-0.040 (0.051)	-0.143** (0.058)	0.206 (0.389)	0.694 (1.056)	-0.152 (0.196)	-0.146 (0.316)
Transportation	0.185** (0.088)	0.184 (0.132)	0.066 (0.060)	0.061 (0.060)	0.657*** (0.172)	0.335 (0.208)	0.173 (0.202)	0.232 (0.254)
Tourism	1.450 (1.255)	1.550 (2.087)	-0.576 (1.056)	-1.593 (2.388)	0.218 (1.003)	0.675 (2.474)	0.887 (0.961)	3.886 (2.810)
Information services	0.092 (0.079)	0.093 (0.099)	-0.021 (0.069)	-0.041 (0.080)	0.003 (0.040)	0.006 (0.048)	1.120 (1.229)	2.529 (2.847)
Knowledge consultancy	-0.035 (0.170)	-0.065 (0.270)	0.052* (0.030)	0.048 (0.031)	0.090 (0.456)	-0.117 (0.582)	0.066 (0.052)	0.051 (0.074)
Business support	-0.273 (0.409)	-0.259 (0.435)	-0.044 (0.046)	-0.007 (0.022)	-0.956 (0.719)	-1.349 (1.179)	-0.118 (0.105)	-0.230 (0.203)

Table B-11: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on allocative efficiency over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge’s estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for firm exits. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

B.3 Robustness Examination on Industry Productivity

In this subappendix, we elaborate on our results on industry productivity, also including further investigations of intra-industrial composition effects related to size. These analyses supplement the investigations of subsection 5.3, where the baseline results are provided in Table 5. Unweighted regressions at firm level and municipality level put the same weight on active firms and municipalities respectively, regardless of their contributions to value creation. Weighted regressions at firm level or municipal level are far from straightforward, given our fixed effect specification with industry-year dummies and standard errors clustered on observations units. An intermediate approach from considering impulses of market access on industry-specific TFP at firm level and municipal level is to apply disaggregate industries as observation units at municipal level as observation units.

In Table B-12, we carry out a modification of our baseline regressions at industry level based on this idea, where the A64 second revision classification is exploited as disaggregate industry classification. As in our baseline regressions, there are seemingly signs of positive impulses on industry TFP from increased regional integration within the manufacturing industries and wholesale and vehicle trade, but these impulses do still not pass the significance test. Also business support services have significant impulse estimates seemingly caused by an underlying trend when only the core study region is included in the regressions. In line with the baseline regressions, knowledge consultancy involves positive impact estimates also after placebo adjustment when we limit ourselves to the core study region, but in this case the estimates turn

significant under the assumption of exponential distance decay. As in our baseline regressions, we also see signs of some significant underlying trends turning and becoming insignificant.

In Table B-13, we have repeated our baseline regressions, but without controlling for relative price developments through our terms of trade control. Underlying trends still seem to explain the increase in TFP for observation units close to road openings in consumer and technological manufacturing and wholesale and vehicle trade. For material manufacturing, the underlying trend is no longer visible, but the impulse estimate is only barely significant under power distance decay and application of just the core study region. Among the service industries, underlying trends still seem to come into play for many of them.

In Table B-14, we have repeated our baseline regression with Levinsohn and Petrin's estimation procedure instead of Wooldridge's procedure. We do not adjust the estimates for potential selection biases related to exit of industries, as the *Prodest* command in Stata does not manage to do so due to computational challenges. In essence, these results show the same as our baseline regressions: Positive impulse estimates for the manufacturing industries and wholesale and vehicle trade do not pass the placebo test, while underlying trends in some other industries do not come out as significant in the impact estimation.

In the robustness checks reported in Table B-15, we consider how the baseline results are affected in case of lower distance decay parameters than in the baseline regressions, lowering the power distance decay parameter δ^{pow} from 2.3 to 1 and the exponential distance decay parameter δ^{exp} from 0.07 to 0.03. This obviously deviates substantially from our estimation in subsection 5.1, but it is more in line with assumptions earlier made in the literature. Some of the Wooldridge estimates appear unreliably high, which is probably due to the procedures' vulnerability for and presence of a combination of few observations and less variation in the data. Again, we obtain positive impact estimates for material and technological manufacturing, as well as for wholesale and vehicle trade. In case of consumer manufacturing, the impact estimates have turned insignificant and even negative with a strong positive underlying trend. Signs of underlying trends were also found in some other industries. This is most apparent for the retail trade industry, where the regression results only building on the core study region suggest that a weak positive underlying trend has been turned to a weak negative one.

In Table B-16 and Table B-17, we have considered how regional integration through new road construction has affected TFP in the masses of lasting firms and entering and exiting firms respectively, measured at municipality level. Within manufacturing, there are few indications of productivity impulses from increased market access for the masses of lasting firms, while the productivity impulses are apparent for the masses of entering and exiting firms with underlying placebo developments coming into play. For wholesale and vehicle trade, both firm masses involve positive impact estimates not passing the placebo test. For retail trade, the municipal masses of lasting firms next to new road constructions have had a negative productivity growth after the related road openings, despite positive underlying trends. Keeping in mind that the masses are measured at municipal level, this development pattern may indicate a restructuring of the retail industry, subsequent to increases in market access induced by road openings. Yet, many of these results are not singular significant. For knowledge consultancy and information services, the regressions involving the mass of lasting firms in the core study region indicate traveling time reductions have caused weak relative productivity improvement locally. In case of the transportation industry, both firm masses faced positive productivity

trends in the placebo period in municipalities close to new road constructions, which turned insignificant involving mostly negative estimates after the new constructions' realization.

As in subappendix B.1, we also consider impulses on components of technical productivity beyond TFP – this time at industry level. Estimates for impulses of increased market access caused by expansion of the road network on scale efficiency and allocative efficiency are reported in Table B-18 and Table B-19 respectively. As the analogous regressions at firm level, these regressions give no indications of positive impulses on scale efficiency or allocative efficiency. Once again, the few significant results from our investigation on the efficiency concepts are clearly caused by underlying development patterns.

Scale properties may suggest an optimal firm size, but more competition could also contribute to outperforming low productivity firms and to increasing activities in high productivity firms. Our background checks with simple linear regressions show tendencies over industries where larger firms have higher labor productivity (measured by labor costs per person engaged or net value added per person engaged) up to certain firm size, but that this pattern is nonlinear. With these reflections in mind, we have explored the possibility that regional integration through road constructions may have affected the firm size in different industries. We have considered average municipal firm size over industries for the masses of all firms and single-branch firms are reported in Table B-20 and Table B-21 respectively.

While the regressions conducted at municipal level reflect the average impact over municipalities, similar regressions at firm level reflect the development for the average firm. To explore the impact of increased market access caused by expansion in the road network on firm size at firm level, we utilize Heckman's correction procedure for selection biases related to exits in all firms, where results are reported in Table B-20. As in our other firm regressions, we apply firm fixed effect, industry-year interaction dummies and clustering of standard errors on firms. In practice, the procedure both requires very high computational power and often involves severe convergence challenges. In our effort to obtain approximate results for this procedure, we have therefore chosen to apply Davidson-Fletcher-Powell's algorithm in the maximization of likelihood function (e.g. Gould, Pitblado and Poi 2010), limited upward to 20 repetitions.⁷ Due to the lack of complete convergence with the weaknesses that follows, we have also applied the same estimation approach without selection correction (i.e. linear panel data regressions), as reported in Table B-21.

Although the tables show some of the same tendencies for single- and multi branch level at aggregate level with mostly insignificant results, they also involve some differences. The most striking finding from these regressions is that the impact estimates for the retail trade industry are negative and significant, when all branch figurations are included. To the contrary, they are

⁷ The Stata command *xheckman*⁴ is developed to handle selection biases for linear regressions on panel data by Heckman's correction procedure. By the estimation procedure, we estimate the probability for exits simultaneously with the impact regression by a Probit regression with gross investments and operational profits from the last period as predictors of exits. In order to take the structural breaks around zero for our predictors into account, we distinguish between positive and negative values. The probability of survival (i.e. being active in the next period, χ) becomes $\text{Prob}(\chi = 1 | I_{i,t-1}^{pos}, I_{i,t-1}^{neg}, r_{i,t-1}^{pos}, r_{i,t-1}^{neg}) = \Phi_{r,t}(I_{i,t-1}^{pos}, I_{i,t-1}^{neg}, r_{i,t-1}^{pos}, r_{i,t-1}^{neg})$, where A is a dummy for being active in the market, $I_{i,t-1}^{pos}$ and $I_{i,t-1}^{neg}$ are positive negative gross investments in fixed capital respectively and, $r_{i,t-1}^{pos}$ and $r_{i,t-1}^{neg}$ are positive and negative operational profits respectively, all measured in fixed prices for study object i at time $t - 1$. $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution.

positive and in one case significant when only single-branch firms are included. This suggests that the retail industry to some extent has restructured towards a larger share of multi-branch firms in areas that have become subject to close expansions in the road network. Among the firm level regressions for the retail industry, only the Heckman estimate on the extended study region with exponential distance decay remains valid after the placebo impact is accounted for.

Mismatch between the regression results for single- and multi-branch firms at municipal firms also occur for the business support industry. Here, there are negative and significant impact estimates on firm size for single-branch firms, but these results are less robust. At firm level, the Heckman regressions (but not the linear panel data regressions) suggest that the firm size for the average firm has increased, although there are some signs of a weak underlying trend within the core study region. The transportation industry shows signs of positive growth in municipal firm size for the mass of single-branch firms and negative size growth in municipal firm size for the mass of all firms, but these results are not separately significant. Both firm masses are subject to weak negative placebo trends, while the impact estimates are insignificant at firm level.

Other tendencies concerning impacts of increased market access induced by road constructions are weak, less robust and on the borderline to be significant if the placebo trend is adjusted for. For the wholesale and vehicle trade, there are signs of a positive trend in firm size that turns negative subsequent to the road expansion, while the opposite tendency is seen for knowledge consultancy. Increase in firm size of the average firm size for wholesale and vehicle trade and knowledge consultancy appears to be just a reflection of underlying development trends. For other industries, changes in firm size do not involve significant results at municipal level, at least not after taking the underlying trend into account, involving consumer manufacturing, information services and tourism. For the two first mentioned industries, similar results are found at firm level. In case of tourism, the firm level regressions produce positive results with and negative results without selection correction, suggesting that firm selection has contributed to consolidation.

Impact on TFP		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region		Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing		3.963 (2.824)	6.767* (3.388)	0.943 (1.907)	1.509 (1.745)	13.960 (16.390)	13.080 (14.450)	9.381* (5.559)	7.677* (4.289)
Material manufacturing		7.432*** (2.439)	5.430** (2.593)	7.592*** (2.324)	5.994*** (2.196)	8.380 (15.710)	5.575 (13.820)	17.08*** (5.972)	11.86*** (4.359)
Technological manufacturing		14.94* (8.559)	9.879* (5.755)	12.92*** (4.934)	8.935** (3.716)	16.260 (21.290)	12.140 (19.440)	10.35* (5.692)	6.201 (4.057)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		2.091 (1.264)	1.389 (1.167)	3.489** (1.573)	2.890** (1.294)	3.091* (1.536)	2.815* (1.392)	13.79** (5.564)	9.117** (3.850)
Retail trade		-0.810 (0.532)	-0.610 (0.694)	2.437 (2.344)	1.177 (1.791)	6.676** (2.274)	5.639** (1.900)	-6.508 (4.252)	-4.900* (2.930)
Transportation		-0.045 (2.370)	0.177 (2.242)	0.503 (1.377)	1.012 (1.070)	-1.565 (5.419)	-1.222 (4.667)	4.412* (2.467)	2.568 (1.675)
Tourism		0.363 (1.961)	1.806 (2.060)	2.190 (2.057)	1.952 (1.546)	-1.359 (6.063)	-4.456 (5.284)	-1.870 (5.026)	-5.005 (4.671)
Information services		2.953 (1.906)	2.767 (1.648)	1.430 (1.664)	0.885 (1.340)	-19.940 (20.380)	-22.660 (16.310)	2.053 (4.743)	2.360 (3.143)
Knowledge consultancy		1.678 (1.039)	2.431** (1.171)	0.588 (0.963)	1.031 (0.940)	-1.843 (4.447)	-1.082 (3.927)	0.175 (2.270)	-0.860 (1.746)
Business support		4.578* (2.347)	5.422** (2.494)	0.531 (1.733)	0.749 (1.503)	3.920 (6.879)	4.160 (6.264)	4.932 (4.974)	4.371 (3.282)

Table B-12: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at interaction A64 industries and municipalities, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, municipality-industry fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with correction for industry closures, but without terms of trade as control variable. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region		Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing		3.520*	7.231*	-0.820	0.114	10.660	9.456	10.660	9.456
		(1.712)	(3.548)	(2.713)	(2.013)	(14.930)	(13.300)	(14.930)	(13.300)
Material manufacturing		6.601*	3.555	4.348	1.340	-8.292	-9.230	-8.292	-9.230
		(3.336)	(4.522)	(2.811)	(2.933)	(6.613)	(6.702)	(6.613)	(6.702)
Technological manufacturing		10.85**	7.380*	10.98***	8.585***	13.58*	9.781*	13.58*	9.781*
		(4.819)	(3.948)	(3.704)	(3.206)	(6.797)	(5.362)	(6.797)	(5.362)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		2.128***	1.469*	3.199**	2.766**	3.076**	3.011**	3.076**	3.011**
		(0.469)	(0.745)	(1.343)	(1.139)	(1.143)	(1.201)	(1.143)	(1.201)
Retail trade		-0.170	0.040	1.043	0.333	3.567*	3.105*	3.567*	3.105*
		(0.333)	(0.398)	(1.289)	(1.171)	(1.921)	(1.583)	(1.921)	(1.583)
Transportation		-0.706	-1.063	-1.526	-1.032	1.038	1.737	1.038	1.737
		(1.096)	(0.966)	(1.709)	(1.169)	(4.026)	(2.682)	(4.026)	(2.682)
Tourism		0.738	1.627	0.367	0.515	-0.035	-1.494	-0.035	-1.494
		(2.276)	(2.130)	(1.675)	(1.363)	(2.468)	(2.282)	(2.468)	(2.282)
Information services		-0.757	-0.323	-0.825	-0.878	-36.92***	-32.19***	-36.92***	-32.19***
		(1.184)	(0.889)	(1.468)	(1.249)	(11.080)	(8.647)	(11.080)	(8.647)
Knowledge consultancy		0.351	0.710	-0.082	-0.217	-0.981	-1.786	-0.981	-1.786
		(0.374)	(0.468)	(1.006)	(1.135)	(1.356)	(1.885)	(1.356)	(1.885)
Business support		-0.327	0.198	0.216	0.121	7.694	7.175	7.694	7.175
		(1.867)	(1.868)	(2.145)	(1.812)	(9.074)	(7.160)	(9.074)	(7.160)

Table B-13: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at municipal level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using year dummies, municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with correction for industry closures, but without terms of trade as control variable. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region		Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing		3.598** (1.683)	7.205* (3.418)	-0.662 (2.659)	0.281 (1.953)	10.950 (14.690)	9.793 (13.140)	21.84*** (6.677)	13.12** (5.418)
Material manufacturing		6.107* (3.043)	3.415 (4.090)	4.540* (2.479)	1.769 (2.590)	-7.980 (6.078)	-8.988 (6.277)	10.12** (4.834)	5.617 (3.637)
Technological manufacturing		11.06** (4.883)	8.022* (4.190)	11.57*** (3.654)	9.221*** (3.205)	15.85** (6.558)	12.18** (5.146)	-1.830 (4.610)	-1.937 (2.702)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		2.182*** (0.489)	1.551* (0.795)	3.297** (1.321)	2.893** (1.120)	2.479** (0.964)	2.445* (1.143)	9.992*** (3.685)	6.923** (3.101)
Retail trade		0.018 (0.321)	0.137 (0.404)	1.322 (1.233)	0.555 (1.075)	2.851 (1.702)	2.365 (1.360)	-0.044 (2.498)	0.165 (1.706)
Transportation		-0.739 (1.153)	-1.094 (1.012)	-1.147 (1.426)	-0.812 (1.065)	1.028 (3.678)	1.547 (2.523)	4.693*** (1.565)	2.240** (1.069)
Tourism		0.720 (2.339)	1.695 (2.191)	1.094 (1.876)	1.056 (1.438)	-0.274 (2.744)	-1.917 (3.273)	5.007 (5.482)	1.116 (3.173)
Information services		-0.853 (1.236)	-0.419 (0.894)	-1.296 (1.558)	-1.246 (1.315)	-34.22** (11.820)	-29.52*** (9.292)	8.336 (5.548)	6.746 (4.153)
Knowledge consultancy		0.264 (0.406)	0.626 (0.505)	-0.180 (0.974)	-0.158 (1.072)	-0.554 (1.060)	-1.411 (1.557)	-2.832 (3.308)	-1.866 (2.683)
Business support		-0.721 (1.827)	-0.131 (1.920)	-0.027 (2.172)	-0.093 (1.837)	7.179 (9.500)	6.638 (7.573)	5.724 (3.557)	3.583* (2.133)

Table B-14: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at municipal level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using year dummies, municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Market access is measured with power di-stance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Levinsohn and Petrin’s estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable, but without correction for industry closures. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region		Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing		0.268	-3.132	-8.719	-3.421	302.200	43.120	72.24***	20.18***
		(25.860)	(5.252)	(10.340)	(3.032)	(213.300)	(31.830)	(21.940)	(6.989)
Material manufacturing		39.42*	2.078	12.690	2.231	-143.300	-32.920	49.27***	3.409
		(19.400)	(6.993)	(8.506)	(2.636)	(80.920)	(22.960)	(16.720)	(5.771)
Technological manufacturing		20.190	5.841	16.13**	6.172**	178.1**	42.74**	6.891	-1.118
		(23.380)	(3.370)	(7.987)	(2.413)	(74.730)	(17.350)	(16.790)	(5.054)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		5.248	1.447	4.209	2.700**	37.130	7.823	34.16***	11.72**
		(6.223)	(0.936)	(4.481)	(1.254)	(26.310)	(5.962)	(12.450)	(4.633)
Retail trade		-8.964*	-1.866*	3.474	-0.092	26.260	11.44*	-5.166	-4.625
		(4.389)	(0.967)	(4.264)	(1.197)	(25.150)	(5.367)	(8.726)	(2.963)
Transportation		-6.831	-3.740*	-3.251	-1.543	-2.522	6.468	19.090	5.668**
		(5.855)	(1.788)	(3.935)	(1.492)	(35.020)	(7.416)	(11.640)	(2.458)
Tourism		-17.020	1.405	0.647	0.804	4.482	5.946	7.581	4.502
		(12.770)	(2.436)	(5.839)	(1.355)	(41.660)	(10.340)	(9.053)	(3.470)
Information services		-24.100	-0.561	-7.082	-0.627	-236.800	-69.97**	27.590	8.882
		(15.900)	(3.078)	(6.463)	(1.830)	(170.000)	(30.350)	(19.460)	(6.600)
Knowledge consultancy		1.658	0.681	1.443	0.313	-6.818	-4.842	0.033	-3.816
		(3.382)	(0.805)	(3.403)	(0.914)	(15.530)	(4.917)	(4.702)	(5.076)
Business support		0.729	2.352	0.173	0.361	-6.097	-0.523	12.100	2.698
		(18.420)	(3.206)	(6.923)	(1.923)	(112.200)	(34.890)	(13.270)	(3.538)

Table B-15: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using year dummies, municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 1$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.03$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure without terms of trade as control variable and correction for firm exits. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP Firm size Industry \ distance key	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	2.322 (2.283) n = 151	3.473 (2.394) n = 151	-1.361 (3.112) n = 856	-1.345 (2.753) n = 856	-7.587 (9.587) n = 60	-6.699 (8.223) n = 60	22.01*** (8.250) n = 384	15.49** (7.163) n = 384
	2.245 (4.350) n = 176	-0.417 (5.528) n = 176	4.177* (2.302) n = 1,017	2.097 (2.783) n = 1,017	-13.56* (6.594) n = 70	-13.33** (5.542) n = 70	6.660 (5.028) n = 459	4.450 (4.351) n = 459
Material manufacturing	-17.410 (14.810) n = 134	-5.598 (9.608) n = 134	4.603 (5.729) n = 781	1.755 (4.997) n = 781	85.360 (60.350) n = 50	106.200 (71.960) n = 50	2.951 (6.166) n = 339	-0.644 (3.413) n = 339
	2.848*** (0.541) n = 175	2.318*** (0.750) n = 175	1.378 (1.287) n = 1,038	1.282 (1.157) n = 1,038	3.597 (2.751) n = 69	2.254 (2.045) n = 69	6.347* (3.455) n = 459	5.165* (2.878) n = 459
Wholesale and vehicle trade	-1.341*** (0.442) n = 176	-1.598* (0.876) n = 176	-2.338 (3.350) n = 1,140	-2.803 (3.490) n = 1,140	7.682*** (1.791) n = 70	7.898*** (1.560) n = 70	6.938 (4.309) n = 511	5.070 (3.883) n = 511
	0.160 (0.864) n = 159	0.645 (1.075) n = 159	0.035 (0.858) n = 1,005	0.337 (0.526) n = 1,005	6.260*** (1.465) n = 65	5.234*** (1.298) n = 65	1.826 (1.823) n = 455	0.591 (0.950) n = 455
Retail trade	3.817 (2.940) n = 132	4.303 (2.816) n = 132	-0.901 (1.977) n = 856	-0.356 (1.608) n = 856	-0.004 (2.252) n = 50	-0.642 (2.148) n = 50	3.764 (3.760) n = 378	0.347 (2.235) n = 378
	3.850 (2.635) n = 125	5.667* (2.932) n = 125	0.042 (1.587) n = 720	0.553 (1.354) n = 720	-95.940 (86.550) n = 50	-100.400 (90.710) n = 50	3.142 (8.049) n = 326	2.913 (4.568) n = 326
Transportation	1.140** (0.447) n = 176	0.800 (0.652) n = 176	-2.190 (2.354) n = 974	-1.845 (1.638) n = 974	-0.931 (2.403) n = 70	-0.676 (1.950) n = 70	-1.426 (1.207) n = 437	-1.756 (1.068) n = 437
	1.955 (2.088) n = 113	2.851 (2.483) n = 113	2.016 (2.441) n = 585	2.339 (2.523) n = 585	-19.910 (21.240) n = 45	-14.040 (20.500) n = 45	6.655 (5.937) n = 259	3.363 (3.522) n = 259
Tourism	3.850 (2.635) n = 125	5.667* (2.932) n = 125	0.042 (1.587) n = 720	0.553 (1.354) n = 720	-95.940 (86.550) n = 50	-100.400 (90.710) n = 50	3.142 (8.049) n = 326	2.913 (4.568) n = 326
	1.140** (0.447) n = 176	0.800 (0.652) n = 176	-2.190 (2.354) n = 974	-1.845 (1.638) n = 974	-0.931 (2.403) n = 70	-0.676 (1.950) n = 70	-1.426 (1.207) n = 437	-1.756 (1.068) n = 437
Information services	1.955 (2.088) n = 113	2.851 (2.483) n = 113	2.016 (2.441) n = 585	2.339 (2.523) n = 585	-19.910 (21.240) n = 45	-14.040 (20.500) n = 45	6.655 (5.937) n = 259	3.363 (3.522) n = 259
	1.140** (0.447) n = 176	0.800 (0.652) n = 176	-2.190 (2.354) n = 974	-1.845 (1.638) n = 974	-0.931 (2.403) n = 70	-0.676 (1.950) n = 70	-1.426 (1.207) n = 437	-1.756 (1.068) n = 437
Knowledge consultancy	1.955 (2.088) n = 113	2.851 (2.483) n = 113	2.016 (2.441) n = 585	2.339 (2.523) n = 585	-19.910 (21.240) n = 45	-14.040 (20.500) n = 45	6.655 (5.937) n = 259	3.363 (3.522) n = 259
	1.140** (0.447) n = 176	0.800 (0.652) n = 176	-2.190 (2.354) n = 974	-1.845 (1.638) n = 974	-0.931 (2.403) n = 70	-0.676 (1.950) n = 70	-1.426 (1.207) n = 437	-1.756 (1.068) n = 437
Business support	1.955 (2.088) n = 113	2.851 (2.483) n = 113	2.016 (2.441) n = 585	2.339 (2.523) n = 585	-19.910 (21.240) n = 45	-14.040 (20.500) n = 45	6.655 (5.937) n = 259	3.363 (3.522) n = 259
	1.140** (0.447) n = 176	0.800 (0.652) n = 176	-2.190 (2.354) n = 974	-1.845 (1.638) n = 974	-0.931 (2.403) n = 70	-0.676 (1.950) n = 70	-1.426 (1.207) n = 437	-1.756 (1.068) n = 437

Table B-16: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at municipal level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using year dummies, municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Limited to lasting firms. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for industry closures. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on TFP Firm size Industry \ distance key	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	12.69*** (2.750) n = 160	11.56** (4.683) n = 160	5.733 (3.936) n = 754	2.603 (4.071) n = 754	39.13*** (8.038) n = 62	32.91*** (7.006) n = 62	14.29* (7.396) n = 344	11.47* (5.919) n = 344
	4.971* (2.774) n = 172	1.003 (2.820) n = 172	5.383** (2.696) n = 889	1.479 (2.887) n = 889	49.95* (27.180) n = 66	43.70* (23.780) n = 66	34.80*** (9.595) n = 393	21.05** (8.526) n = 393
Technological manufacturing	11.980 (7.639) n = 131	6.407 (7.463) n = 131	9.896*** (3.550) n = 606	6.622 (4.017) n = 606	1.576 (15.050) n = 50	-3.606 (15.940) n = 50	6.317 (7.406) n = 274	5.641 (4.904) n = 274
Wholesale and vehicle trade	-1.872 (1.176) n = 176	-0.809 (1.744) n = 176	1.140 (2.958) n = 979	0.674 (2.261) n = 979	2.309 (5.083) n = 70	1.506 (6.267) n = 70	15.47*** (4.327) n = 424	11.50** (4.692) n = 424
Retail trade	-0.521 (1.386) n = 176	-0.675 (2.454) n = 176	0.188 (2.382) n = 1,095	1.441 (1.738) n = 1,095	-11.800 (13.180) n = 70	-11.520 (11.680) n = 70	-4.659 (3.952) n = 477	-1.030 (3.545) n = 477
Transportation	-1.192 (2.242) n = 161	-2.478 (2.071) n = 161	-0.645 (2.090) n = 919	-0.680 (1.596) n = 919	2.140 (3.964) n = 64	2.552 (3.110) n = 64	6.471*** (1.829) n = 393	4.510*** (1.424) n = 393
Tourism	-2.823 (2.485) n = 163	-0.198 (2.646) n = 163	1.631 (2.601) n = 937	1.654 (1.865) n = 937	-3.309 (14.760) n = 62	0.353 (13.960) n = 62	4.693 (5.430) n = 391	1.582 (3.591) n = 391
Information services	-2.113 (2.082) n = 139	-3.192 (2.519) n = 139	-2.886 (2.180) n = 632	-3.217* (1.813) n = 632	-9.314 (16.290) n = 47	-11.400 (11.060) n = 47	7.012 (8.242) n = 265	7.186 (8.776) n = 265
Knowledge consultancy	-0.035 (1.743) n = 169	1.319 (1.700) n = 169	1.162 (1.832) n = 1,066	1.645 (1.760) n = 1,066	-1.031 (3.497) n = 63	-3.412 (4.934) n = 63	2.112 (3.651) n = 465	1.076 (3.194) n = 465
Business support	-1.285 (1.675) n = 145	-0.767 (2.099) n = 145	-0.370 (2.399) n = 760	-0.422 (2.040) n = 760	9.519 (6.849) n = 54	8.270 (5.866) n = 54	3.100 (4.517) n = 291	1.935 (2.623) n = 291

Table B-17: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on TFP over industries at municipal level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using year dummies, municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Limited to entering and exiting firms. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for industry closures. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on scale efficiency		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region		Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing		0.095 (0.077)	0.002 (0.175)	-0.010 (0.119)	-0.057 (0.106)	0.021 (0.191)	0.054 (0.177)	-0.228 (0.169)	-0.236* (0.131)
Material manufacturing		-0.242 (0.308)	0.065 (0.334)	0.195 (0.420)	0.365 (0.343)	-0.499 (0.549)	-0.355 (0.410)	0.459 (0.281)	0.372* (0.211)
Technological manufacturing		0.133 (0.966)	0.053 (0.433)	0.120 (0.419)	0.110 (0.298)	-0.118 (0.836)	-0.181 (0.864)	0.101 (0.160)	0.086 (0.109)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		0.005 (0.004)	0.001 (0.006)	-0.005 (0.014)	-0.004 (0.012)	-0.002 (0.024)	-0.001 (0.021)	-0.025 (0.029)	-0.017 (0.026)
Retail trade		0.028** (0.010)	0.035** (0.014)	0.034** (0.014)	0.022* (0.011)	0.020 (0.029)	0.008 (0.020)	0.026 (0.017)	0.021 (0.014)
Transportation		-0.009 (0.014)	-0.003 (0.016)	-0.003 (0.013)	0.009 (0.011)	-0.037 (0.052)	-0.017 (0.035)	-0.046** (0.023)	-0.034** (0.014)
Tourism		0.016 (0.030)	0.041 (0.054)	-0.015 (0.032)	-0.004 (0.025)	0.027 (0.137)	0.027 (0.117)	-0.043 (0.048)	-0.062 (0.040)
Information services		-0.008 (0.052)	-0.003 (0.060)	-0.119 (0.098)	-0.014 (0.092)	0.225 (0.571)	0.275 (0.426)	-0.039 (0.149)	-0.035 (0.101)
Knowledge consultancy		-0.001 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	0.009 (0.005)	0.011* (0.005)	0.000 (0.011)	-0.005 (0.010)
Business support		0.113 (0.102)	0.048 (0.129)	0.123* (0.067)	0.089 (0.076)	0.077 (0.091)	0.080 (0.077)	-0.020 (0.070)	0.009 (0.049)

Table B-18: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on scale efficiency over industries at municipal level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using year dummies, municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for industry closures. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on allocative eff.		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region		Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing		7.787 (13.880)	21.380 (19.370)	-16.340 (17.820)	-9.032 (9.406)	-0.962 (1.052)	-1.228* (0.639)	0.612 (0.740)	0.486 (0.532)
Material manufacturing		-0.653 (1.025)	0.195 (1.717)	-16.160 (24.400)	0.054 (9.125)	-0.095 (0.390)	-0.072 (0.381)	2.873 (3.531)	1.632 (1.790)
Technological manufacturing		-0.013 (2.396)	-1.027 (0.941)	-10.810 (11.520)	-6.305 (6.586)	-1.834 (1.149)	-0.915 (1.593)	-0.393 (0.666)	-0.259 (0.402)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		-0.083 (0.061)	-0.040 (0.077)	0.721 (0.621)	0.457 (0.467)	0.074 (0.136)	0.070 (0.119)	-0.341 (0.278)	-0.277 (0.225)
Retail trade		0.048 (0.029)	0.049 (0.035)	2.779 (2.742)	2.750 (2.706)	-0.070 (0.047)	-0.031 (0.044)	-0.269 (0.184)	-0.350 (0.289)
Transportation		-0.056 (0.107)	-0.042 (0.194)	-0.022 (0.182)	-0.136 (0.154)	0.063 (0.482)	-0.059 (0.306)	0.304 (0.286)	0.172 (0.158)
Tourism		0.054 (0.409)	0.389 (0.618)	-4.111 (2.674)	-3.278* (1.780)	-0.561* (0.313)	-0.489* (0.238)	0.581 (0.961)	0.230 (0.589)
Information services		-2.880 (2.951)	-4.079 (3.255)	0.386 (1.087)	0.245 (1.198)	17.690 (11.250)	19.21* (9.583)	-0.254 (0.809)	0.087 (0.400)
Knowledge consultancy		0.143*** (0.038)	0.093 (0.073)	1.210 (1.367)	1.168 (1.224)	0.348 (0.296)	0.370 (0.310)	-0.710 (0.787)	-0.985 (0.775)
Business support		-0.846 (3.201)	-2.698 (3.893)	-2.308 (2.628)	-2.930 (2.495)	-0.930 (0.533)	-0.842* (0.469)	-2.094 (3.804)	-0.291 (1.206)

Table B-19: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on allocative efficiency over industries at municipal level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using year dummies, municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). TFP is pre-estimated by Wooldridge's estimation procedure with terms of trade as control variable and correction for industry closures. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on firm size		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	
Consumer manufacturing	2.004*	0.069	0.249	-0.267	0.579	0.090	-0.556	-0.225	
	(1.082)	(1.763)	(1.476)	(1.251)	(3.754)	(3.724)	(1.225)	(1.042)	
Material manufacturing	-0.277	0.404	-0.836	-0.333	1.615	1.448*	1.898**	1.530**	
	(0.687)	(0.815)	(0.864)	(0.785)	(0.980)	(0.795)	(0.947)	(0.728)	
Technological manufacturing	-1.879	-4.531*	-0.727	-1.382	0.025	0.080	1.147	0.409	
	(3.908)	(2.295)	(2.964)	(2.648)	(3.969)	(3.604)	(2.209)	(1.599)	
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.608	-0.020	1.236	0.755	-0.865	-0.638	-0.646	-1.085	
	(0.354)	(0.716)	(0.978)	(0.841)	(1.913)	(1.612)	(1.003)	(0.861)	
Retail trade	1.493**	0.329	0.148	-0.113	-1.335	-1.197	-0.799	-0.296	
	(0.640)	(1.019)	(0.938)	(0.664)	(0.868)	(0.815)	(0.800)	(0.613)	
Transportation	-0.413	-1.046	-0.250	-0.735	1.460	1.314	3.038**	2.567**	
	(1.452)	(1.703)	(1.437)	(1.214)	(3.852)	(3.245)	(1.405)	(1.008)	
Tourism	2.103**	1.174	0.955	0.716	4.647	4.411	1.618	1.568	
	(0.856)	(1.373)	(1.500)	(1.214)	(3.782)	(3.019)	(1.452)	(1.233)	
Information services	-0.254	-0.838	-0.806	-0.864	3.238	2.991	-3.648	-2.839*	
	(0.813)	(0.845)	(1.111)	(1.059)	(3.072)	(2.373)	(2.494)	(1.501)	
Knowledge consultancy	-1.565**	-1.935**	0.222	0.613	1.997	1.671	2.173**	1.311	
	(0.703)	(0.706)	(0.956)	(0.903)	(1.906)	(1.705)	(1.064)	(0.872)	
Business support	2.266	-1.025	-0.032	-0.762	5.004	4.334	-1.446	-1.556	
	(3.171)	(3.948)	(2.770)	(2.607)	(3.784)	(3.707)	(2.240)	(1.959)	

Table B-20: Firm size measured by number of persons engaged in the mass of single- and multi-branch firms. Estimated by using linear panel data regressions with year dummies and municipality fixed effects. (* for p < 0.1, ** for p < 0.05 and * for p < 0.01)**

Impact on firm size		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	
Consumer manufacturing	2.367	1.380	1.215	0.913	-0.295	-0.216	0.264	-0.610	
	(1.382)	(2.041)	(1.493)	(1.510)	(3.709)	(3.277)	(2.023)	(1.238)	
Material manufacturing	-1.659	-0.264	0.627	1.359	0.499	0.776	2.989*	2.248*	
	(2.024)	(1.918)	(2.288)	(1.781)	(2.085)	(1.866)	(1.556)	(1.172)	
Technological manufacturing	-2.744	-4.471*	0.219	-0.111	0.887	1.611	1.586	1.453	
	(4.095)	(2.407)	(2.897)	(2.505)	(5.101)	(3.760)	(1.686)	(1.153)	
Wholesale and vehicle trade	1.315**	0.822	1.182	0.894	-0.278	-0.499	-1.660	-0.953	
	(0.537)	(0.790)	(1.073)	(0.967)	(2.802)	(2.280)	(1.367)	(1.030)	
Retail trade	-1.567**	-1.715**	-1.465*	-1.187**	-0.699	-0.063	-0.634	-0.248	
	(0.562)	(0.751)	(0.741)	(0.596)	(1.104)	(0.751)	(0.757)	(0.555)	
Transportation	1.535	0.326	0.610	-0.040	7.959	4.510	8.034***	5.423***	
	(2.164)	(2.476)	(1.678)	(1.497)	(8.196)	(5.332)	(2.549)	(1.980)	
Tourism	0.645	0.438	1.195	0.885	3.104	2.865	2.365	2.581*	
	(0.921)	(1.223)	(1.257)	(1.076)	(3.573)	(3.032)	(1.427)	(1.416)	
Information services	0.451	0.163	-1.481	-1.183	20.58***	18.94***	-0.184	-0.559	
	(1.138)	(1.324)	(1.262)	(1.035)	(5.623)	(3.533)	(2.842)	(1.559)	
Knowledge consultancy	-0.103	-0.421	1.130	1.199	2.807	2.597*	1.848	0.849	
	(0.597)	(0.702)	(1.026)	(0.840)	(1.605)	(1.284)	(1.948)	(1.491)	
Business support	-6.346***	-5.149*	-4.238**	-2.568	0.284	-0.089	0.057	-0.189	
	(1.972)	(2.563)	(2.069)	(2.267)	(9.465)	(8.343)	(3.728)	(2.669)	

Table B-21: Firm size measured by number of persons engaged in the mass of single-branch firms. Estimated by using linear panel data regressions with year dummies and municipality fixed effects. (* for p < 0.1, ** for p < 0.05 and * for p < 0.01)**

Impact on Firm size		Impact				Placebo			
Distance decay		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ Study region		Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing		0.323 (0.199)	0.365 (0.223)	1.107*** (0.253)	0.944*** (0.276)	0.194** (0.096)	0.157 (0.108)	0.136 (0.163)	0.133 (0.181)
Material manufacturing		0.647 (0.408)	0.995** (0.413)	1.154 (1.014)	1.997* (1.038)	-0.045 (0.067)	-0.027 (0.067)	0.215 (0.155)	0.283 (0.200)
Technological manufacturing		0.050 (0.201)	-0.155 (0.274)	0.258** (0.130)	0.397* (0.223)	0.008 (0.130)	0.114 (0.242)	-0.060 (0.163)	-0.052 (0.245)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		0.157 (0.143)	0.201 (0.195)	-0.118 (0.182)	-0.165 (0.258)	0.066* (0.035)	0.068** (0.034)	0.015 (0.060)	0.017 (0.060)
Retail trade		0.113 (0.090)	0.132 (0.104)	0.075 (0.116)	0.042 (0.133)	0.056 (0.039)	0.065 (0.042)	0.053 (0.062)	0.027 (0.072)
Transportation		-0.057 (0.213)	-0.101 (0.263)	1.200 (1.128)	0.716 (1.088)	0.083 (0.080)	0.058 (0.073)	0.232 (0.151)	0.173 (0.148)
Tourism		-0.416* (0.212)	-0.661** (0.285)	-0.114 (0.123)	-0.353** (0.146)	-0.101 (0.110)	-0.126* (0.068)	-0.094 (0.207)	-0.272** (0.124)
Information services		0.290 (0.176)	0.128 (0.243)	0.450 (0.431)	0.482 (0.601)	0.184*** (0.063)	0.154** (0.068)	0.146* (0.077)	0.096* (0.057)
Knowledge consultancy		0.165** (0.073)	0.135** (0.055)	-0.051 (0.104)	-0.049 (0.099)	0.063* (0.035)	0.014 (0.040)	0.075 (0.060)	0.055 (0.068)
Business support		0.033 (0.264)	-0.003 (0.301)	-0.012 (0.328)	0.038 (0.400)	-0.020 (0.062)	-0.006 (0.049)	-0.033 (0.106)	-0.033 (0.107)

Table B-22: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on firm size over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using industry-specific year dummies, firm fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on Firm size Distance decay Industry \ Study region	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	0.220** (0.089)	0.214** (0.089)	0.069* (0.035)	0.065** (0.030)	0.222** (0.111)	0.198* (0.104)	0.096*** (0.036)	0.027 (0.029)
Material manufacturing	0.179 (0.219)	0.214 (0.210)	-0.029 (0.037)	0.005 (0.028)	0.037 (0.264)	0.042 (0.236)	0.074* (0.039)	0.037 (0.030)
Technological manufacturing	0.029 (0.125)	-0.021 (0.123)	-0.032 (0.053)	-0.010 (0.059)	-0.092 (0.123)	-0.075 (0.138)	-0.099** (0.046)	-0.119*** (0.040)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.104 (0.069)	0.104 (0.068)	0.063*** (0.017)	0.065*** (0.015)	-0.091 (0.063)	0.007 (0.061)	0.105*** (0.018)	-0.025 (0.016)
Retail trade	0.043 (0.033)	0.071** (0.032)	-0.002 (0.013)	0.042*** (0.010)	0.056 (0.035)	0.072** (0.035)	0.007 (0.012)	0.015 (0.010)
Transportation	0.042 (0.106)	-0.007 (0.124)	0.080*** (0.031)	0.017 (0.022)	0.324*** (0.118)	0.232* (0.131)	0.103*** (0.031)	-0.040 (0.024)
Tourism	0.031 (0.069)	0.056 (0.064)	0.108*** (0.020)	0.083*** (0.016)	0.204*** (0.068)	0.143** (0.063)	0.105*** (0.025)	0.107*** (0.023)
Information services	0.167** (0.075)	0.134* (0.073)	0.145*** (0.032)	0.075** (0.033)	0.138 (0.086)	0.115 (0.079)	0.160*** (0.028)	0.006 (0.025)
Knowledge consultancy	0.148*** (0.041)	0.134*** (0.032)	0.065*** (0.015)	0.028* (0.016)	0.047 (0.039)	0.089** (0.038)	0.123*** (0.016)	0.011 (0.014)
Business support	0.196* (0.113)	0.213** (0.104)	0.091*** (0.028)	0.078*** (0.023)	0.073 (0.117)	0.119 (0.114)	0.035 (0.035)	0.005 (0.031)

Table B-23: Impacts and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on firm size over industries at firm level, estimated by linear panel data regressions using Heckman correction for handling selection biases associated with exits, industry-specific year dummies, random fixed effects and clustered standard errors on firms. Positive and negative gross investments in fixed capital and positive and negative net operational profits are used to predict exits. The Davidson-Fletcher-Powell (DFP) algorithm is applied to estimate the maximum likelihood with 20 repetitions regardless of progress in convergence. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

B.4 Robustness Examination on Industry Composition Effects

In this subappendix, we carry out robustness checks to our analyses on industry composition effects related to employment, in addition to considering changes in fixed capital intensity. These investigations supplement the examinations of subsection 5.4, where overall regional patterns of Coastal Southern Norway were discussed in relation to Table 6 and the local impulses from road constructions were discussed in relation to Table 7.

Opposed to other economic variables, we have access to reliable employment figures at branch level also for multi-branch firms. In our baseline analyses, we have therefore considered both single- and multi-branch firms. In Table B-24, we assess the overall movement of labor across sectors over the study period for just single-branch firms. Compared to our baseline regressions, the growth patterns for single-branch firms are strikingly different within periods. Furthermore, we consider how the growth employment shares measured in percentage points before and after 2008 have changed, relative to the rest of our extended study region. Compared our baseline regressions, material manufacturing and the trade industries still shown signs of relative higher growth in employment shares after 2008 when only single-branch firms are considered, while the relative change in growth hold the opposite sign for the information service industries. Among the industries with relative declining growth for Coastal Southern Norway in our

baseline analyses, the shares are still falling relatively more after 2008 for knowledge consultancy, tourism and business support services when only single-branch firms are considered, the sign of the relative improvement turns for technological manufacturing. Overall, the striking and unsystematic differences between developments in employment compositions for single- and multi-branch firms support our conclusion in the main paper that there are no overall inter-industry composition effects at regional level at play.

In Table B-25, we consider how municipal employment shares have been affected by increased market access through new road constructions, opposed to the baseline regression only involving single-branch firms. Again, the results become very different when only single-branch firms are considered. Wholesale and vehicle trade suddenly involve significant and positive impulse estimates from increased market access. Furthermore, the significant positive impulse estimates associated with the retail industry are turned to significant and negative, although they become insignificant and positive if the placebo impact is subtracted. The impulse estimates for the knowledge consultancy are still negative compared to the placebo development, but they are no longer significant. Again, the lack of clear tendencies and robustness are the most striking finding, when comparing the analyses with and without multi-branch firms. We remind the readers that the descriptive statistics provided in subsection 4.1 suggested a weak growth in single-branch firms' employment share over our study period.

In Table B-26, we address changes in capital intensity over industries measured by fixed capital services per person engaged. These results show few clear indications of changes in capital intensity due to road openings, although some estimates under power distance are significant different from the placebo trend, when only the core study region is applied.

In Table B-27, we have replaced employment shares with employment stock as outcome variable compare the baseline regressions. The most considerable difference in the results is that the impulse estimate for business support services come out as negative. The results for knowledge consultancy turn insignificant, but they still reflect the same tendency after the placebo impact is accounted for. The results for the trade industries are in principle the same.

Impact on employment	Relative labor cost level		Share of employment in single-branch firms					
	Average 2004-2014		Status 2004		Annual growth 2004-2008		Annual growth 2008-2014	
	Core	Extended except core	Core	Extended except core	Core	Extended except core	Core	Extended except core
Consumer manufacturing	0.9913	1.0527	0.0626	0.0735	-0.0029	-0.0014	0.0001	-0.0012
Material manufacturing	1.2742	1.2121	0.1399	0.1071	0.0004	-0.0012	-0.0022	-0.0038
Technological manufacturing	1.2471	1.3252	0.0604	0.0689	-0.0023	-0.0007	-0.0024	-0.0016
Wholesale and vehicle trade	1.1828	1.1867	0.1554	0.1556	-0.0027	-0.0012	0.0006	-0.0006
Retail trade	0.6523	0.6382	0.2146	0.2000	-0.0039	-0.0020	0.0001	-0.0031
Transportation	1.0871	1.0808	0.0823	0.0829	-0.0013	-0.0010	-0.0021	0.0009
Tourism	0.5757	0.6076	0.1137	0.1098	0.0045	0.0024	0.0024	0.0010
Information services	1.4287	1.3847	0.0441	0.0469	0.0008	0.0002	-0.0011	0.0009
Knowledge consultancy	1.3266	1.2943	0.0827	0.0947	0.0043	0.0013	0.0008	0.0009
Business support	0.8874	0.8637	0.0441	0.0606	0.0032	0.0035	0.0037	0.0065

Table B-24: Annual growth in employment shares in single firms across industries measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labors costs and initial employment shares. The shares are limited to our industry selection. Labor costs are deflated with basis in average cost levels from 1999 to 2014. Comparison between Coastal Southern Norway (core study region) and municipalities in neighboring counties. Industries with higher labor costs or growth in employment share than the benchmark region are indicated by green color.

Impact on employment	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	0.111 (0.070)	0.055 (0.099)	0.115 (0.082)	0.088 (0.080)	-0.095 (0.129)	-0.030 (0.114)	-0.171 (0.139)	-0.195** (0.096)
Material manufacturing	0.004 (0.258)	0.179 (0.248)	-0.095 (0.221)	0.013 (0.205)	-0.274 (0.309)	-0.262 (0.281)	0.142 (0.249)	0.113 (0.203)
Technological manufacturing	-0.221 (0.309)	-0.270 (0.176)	-0.090 (0.187)	-0.079 (0.152)	-0.051 (0.118)	0.001 (0.101)	-0.008 (0.142)	-0.031 (0.092)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	0.426*** (0.074)	0.292* (0.143)	0.296** (0.127)	0.191 (0.118)	-0.017 (0.371)	0.022 (0.340)	-0.394 (0.301)	-0.225 (0.174)
Retail trade	-0.294** (0.103)	-0.326** (0.152)	-0.349** (0.141)	-0.352** (0.136)	-0.569* (0.278)	-0.361 (0.303)	-0.459*** (0.166)	-0.334*** (0.127)
Transportation	0.142 (0.151)	0.058 (0.167)	0.049 (0.142)	-0.021 (0.121)	0.580 (0.415)	0.350 (0.271)	1.181* (0.633)	0.952** (0.448)
Tourism	-0.024 (0.078)	0.020 (0.071)	0.160 (0.127)	0.165 (0.111)	0.143 (0.361)	0.067 (0.347)	0.077 (0.146)	0.048 (0.163)
Information services	-0.053 (0.079)	-0.064 (0.076)	-0.072 (0.078)	-0.124 (0.077)	0.269** (0.118)	0.218** (0.100)	-0.939 (0.699)	-0.502 (0.382)
Knowledge consultancy	-0.042 (0.041)	-0.030 (0.058)	-0.016 (0.082)	-0.023 (0.084)	0.073 (0.117)	0.082 (0.102)	0.139 (0.170)	0.112 (0.122)
Business support	-0.226 (0.142)	-0.020 (0.243)	-0.263** (0.124)	-0.111 (0.119)	0.179 (0.264)	0.165 (0.225)	-0.003 (0.183)	0.014 (0.158)

Table B-25: Impact and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on municipal employment shares in single-branch firms over industries, estimated by linear panel data regressions using municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). Core region: Coastal Southern Norway. Extended region: Coastal Southern Norway and municipalities in neighboring counties not located next to road openings. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on capital services		Impact				Placebo			
Study region		Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Industry \ distance decay		Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing		-2.076*** (0.689)	-0.574 (1.423)	0.421 (1.491)	1.232 (1.369)	-0.537 (2.319)	0.621 (2.188)	0.796 (2.196)	0.815 (1.365)
Material manufacturing		-0.509 (1.482)	-1.972 (2.214)	0.278 (1.279)	0.239 (1.460)	2.536 (8.399)	1.914 (7.097)	2.975 (2.251)	2.058 (1.460)
Technological manufacturing		6.494 (4.303)	5.537** (2.521)	1.558 (2.283)	1.317 (1.665)	10.640 (7.438)	8.748 (6.522)	-0.587 (3.274)	-0.589 (1.909)
Wholesale and vehicle trade		1.241*** (0.359)	0.011 (0.847)	0.158 (1.023)	-0.476 (0.899)	0.074 (1.752)	-0.096 (1.548)	4.138** (2.054)	2.170 (1.458)
Retail trade		0.102 (0.496)	-0.487 (0.603)	1.424 (1.331)	1.027 (1.077)	-4.365 (3.596)	-4.364 (3.504)	-1.267 (1.082)	-1.300* (0.756)
Transportation		1.249 (2.607)	-1.115 (3.157)	1.300 (1.511)	0.250 (1.359)	-3.439 (3.639)	-2.099 (3.169)	0.015 (2.420)	0.540 (2.144)
Tourism		0.679 (1.437)	-0.181 (1.764)	-3.664* (2.163)	-2.919* (1.753)	-12.910 (7.551)	-11.01* (6.151)	-6.266** (2.583)	-4.039** (1.615)
Information services		-3.146 (3.368)	-1.271 (4.440)	3.377 (4.531)	3.247 (3.374)	-17.920 (28.460)	-28.230 (24.860)	-4.260 (3.468)	-1.167 (2.436)
Knowledge consultancy		-0.832 (1.102)	-0.379 (1.550)	0.338 (1.746)	0.417 (1.610)	-3.248 (5.262)	-2.411 (5.152)	4.357 (2.659)	3.324** (1.604)
Business support		5.785** (2.651)	4.210 (3.978)	2.843 (2.430)	2.549 (2.944)	17.170 (12.960)	18.660 (13.380)	2.419 (4.856)	-0.369 (3.564)

Table B-26: Impact and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on municipal fixed capital services per person engaged in single-branch firms over industries, estimated by linear panel data regressions using municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Fixed capital services are deflated with basis in the average price levels from 1999 to 2014. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). Core region: Coastal Southern Norway. Extended region: Coastal Southern Norway and municipalities in neighboring counties not located next to road openings. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Study region Industry \ distance decay	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Consumer manufacturing	2.367 (1.382)	1.380 (2.041)	1.215 (1.493)	0.913 (1.510)	0.887 (2.678)	1.970 (2.713)	0.298 (2.022)	-0.532 (1.240)
Material manufacturing	-1.659 (2.024)	-0.264 (1.918)	0.627 (2.288)	1.359 (1.781)	-1.535 (2.780)	-0.813 (2.135)	2.784* (1.554)	2.145* (1.164)
Technological manufacturing	-2.744 (4.095)	-4.471* (2.407)	0.219 (2.897)	-0.111 (2.505)	0.270 (5.011)	0.497 (4.255)	1.531 (1.677)	1.363 (1.147)
Wholesale and vehicle trade	1.315** (0.537)	0.822 (0.790)	1.182 (1.073)	0.894 (0.967)	-0.087 (2.990)	-0.085 (2.546)	-1.627 (1.368)	-0.923 (1.023)
Retail trade	-1.567** (0.562)	-1.715** (0.751)	-1.465* (0.741)	-1.187** (0.596)	-0.612 (0.969)	-0.019 (0.781)	-0.638 (0.753)	-0.259 (0.554)
Transportation	1.535 (2.164)	0.326 (2.476)	0.610 (1.678)	-0.040 (1.497)	7.199 (7.591)	3.920 (4.858)	7.939*** (2.553)	5.358*** (1.978)
Tourism	0.645 (0.921)	0.438 (1.223)	1.195 (1.257)	0.885 (1.076)	1.956 (4.594)	0.982 (4.407)	2.244 (1.427)	2.464* (1.430)
Information services	0.451 (1.138)	0.163 (1.324)	-1.481 (1.262)	-1.183 (1.035)	19.00** (6.688)	15.94** (5.598)	-0.183 (2.823)	-0.550 (1.549)
Knowledge consultancy	-0.103 (0.597)	-0.421 (0.702)	1.130 (1.026)	1.199 (0.840)	3.492** (1.404)	3.436** (1.257)	1.868 (1.938)	0.864 (1.484)
Business support	-6.346*** (1.972)	-5.149* (2.563)	-4.238** (2.069)	-2.568 (2.267)	0.390 (9.587)	0.343 (8.323)	0.147 (3.715)	-0.117 (2.669)

Table B-27: Impact and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on municipal employment stocks in single and multi-branch over industries, estimated by linear panel data regressions using municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). Core region: Coastal Southern Norway. Extended region: Coastal Southern Norway and municipalities in neighboring counties not located next to road openings. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

B.5 Robustness Examination on Regional Composition Effects

Here, we supplement the investigations in subsection 5.5 on regional composition effects with further examinations on impulses on commuting, regional work division, labor participation and fixed capital holdings.

In relation to Figure 8 in the main text, we assessed the commuting patterns into and out from Kristiansand in context of the renewal of European Route 18 August 2009. In Figure B-3 a), we look more closely at outgoing commuting rates within Southern Aust-Agder, which can be considered in relation to the same opening. We see that the commuting rates after the road opening increased from Lillesand to Grimstad and Arendal, and vice versa, but not very much. The relocation of the Norwegian Communications Authority to Lillesand May 2007 apparently also shows in the figure. In Figure B-3 b), we illustrate the changes in commuting patterns within the Lister Region. The depicted increases in commuting can be seen in relation to the opening of European Route 39 between Lyngdal (rural) and Flekkefjord (town) August 2006, and the opening of County Route 465 in Vest-Agder between Kvinesdal (rural) and Farsund (town) from November 2009 to October 2012. We see that the commuting from the rural municipalities increased somewhat into the town they became more connected to subsequent to the road investments, but the levels remained low.

In Table B-28, we consider changes in outgoing commuting rates between municipalities of Coastal Aust-Agder more systematically. The objective of this investigation is to get a rough

overview over the magnitude of possible impacts on regional value creation through higher commuting induced by expansions in the road network. On the left hand side and in the middle of the table, we have shown the status in terms of levels and outgoing commuting shares between the municipalities affected the most by each major road opening in the region, both before and after the road openings. In following two columns (to the middle right of the table), we have depicted the growth in commuting shares, which are expressed in growth in percentage points over the study period. In the right of these two columns, we have adjusted the growth figures for commuting rates for the employment growth in working places not related to the municipalities that become more integrated with them (i.e. not related to municipalities pinpointed in the table).

In the two columns to the right, we have considered commuting gains in terms of possible higher labor cost levels in Kristiansand than at the municipalities of residence. The idea is that similar labor inputs may yield different dividends at different locations, although we obviously do not have data to ensure proper causal identification in this study. Furthermore, possible gains from commuting are not always reflected in our simple comparison of labor costs levels. Considering that we do not have access to data on individuals, or educational or occupational data for that matter, we have to settle for a rough approximation based on the heterogeneities captured by industry structure. To account for differences in industry structure, we weight the industry-specific labor cost levels at the workplace municipalities in accordance with the industry composition of each municipality of residence.⁸

To the far right of this table, we have adjusted the commuting gains by taking traveling costs into account (i.e. such that the ratios represent the net gains rather the gross gains), applying the public framework for transportation appraisal valid in the project's planning period.⁹ Here, we have restricted the net gains for new commuters to be minimum zero (otherwise the new

⁸ For municipality r , we set the counterfactual wage level for workers at residence municipality r at workplace municipality s to $z_{r,s} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=2004}^{T=2014} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N w_{s,i,t} \frac{n_{r,i,t}}{n_{r,t}} \right)$, where $w_{s,i,t}$ is wage level in industry i at alternative workplace municipality s at time t , $n_{r,i,t}$ is employment in industry i and residence municipality r at time t . In our somewhat rough approach, we consider the average wage levels over the whole study period. We apply our rough industry classification consisting of ten industries, as workers often can reallocate relatively between similar industries and as a more disaggregated industry classification would involve challenges with industries not being present in the workplace municipality. All industries in our aggregate industry classification are present in all municipalities in some years, but in some few instances they are not present for all years. In this case, we approximate their industry-specific labor costs levels based on adjacent observations for the industry in the workplace municipality in question and the industry's development in labor costs for the whole study region. Although commuters obviously may commute to other industries, we limit ourselves to our selected industries in this investigation, as the excluded industries often either involve much cyclical noise (i.e. resource industries and finance) or vary little over geography (i.e. public industries and private non-profit industries).

⁹ The economic appraisal framework for transportation measures at the time, including guidance for cost-benefit analysis, is given by Norwegian Ministry of Finance (2005) and Norwegian Public Road Administration (2006a). Key assumptions applied in our study include a discount rate of 0.06, a deflation rate of 0.02, an analysis period of 25 years and a traveling time cost for commuters corresponding to NOK 59.16 in fixed prices at average price level from 1999 to 2014. In our estimation of annual traveling time costs, we have utilized the Norwegian holiday laws and collective agreements which imply a full time equivalent of 227.32 workdays. With regard to labor taxes, we have assumed a labor income tax rate of 28 percent and a pay roll tax rate of 14.1 percent, which were the standard tax rates in Norway at the time of our study. The social expenses – which are not subject to labor income taxation – are assumed to constitute 4 percent of labor costs after the pay roll tax is paid. Based on the Norwegian Ministry of Finance's (2004) white paper on economic outlooks for the Norwegian economy and in line with the concurrent appraisal practice, we assume an annual productivity growth (with stable labor share) of 1.5 percent and an annual population growth of 2 percent (with stable employment share).

commuters would abstain from commuting) and the reductions in private traveling time costs (otherwise the new commuters would already have been commuting) with a mark-up for labor income taxes and pay roll taxes (which the commuters do not take into account). Other gains of commuting that the workers do not account for (e.g. gains for capital owners) are not addressed. Note that traveling time cost savings for existing commuters have already been taken into account by the projects' conventional cost-benefit analysis.

Our back of the envelope considerations on changes in commuting patterns after the road openings suggest that the main potential gains are related to commuting from Coastal Aust-Agder to Kristiansand and the opening of European Route 18. This is also the route and commuting direction with the most and highest absolute increase in commuting. We also see some sign of relatively strong increases in commuting between the municipalities in Coastal Aust-Agder (except for to Birkenes, which is a rather rural municipality), between Flekkefjord and Lyngdal at European Route 39 and between Farsund and Kvinesdal at County Route 465 in Vest-Agder. Yet, as indicated, the benefits for such commuting are mostly not visible in our rough analysis, and commuting shares are also generally lower between these municipalities.

Given our assumptions, we approximate the gain of commuting from the coastal municipalities of Aust-Agder to Kristiansand to be NOK 0.52 million at average price level from 1999 to 2014 in 2010. Given our rough regional GDP estimates and estimated increases in market access (confer our concluding discussion in section 6), this corresponds to a contribution to the agglomeration elasticity of just 0.00001. Starting at the last tertial of 2009 and lasting 25 years, this amounts to NOK 9.39 million in fixed prices, again the average period from 1999 to 2014 as basis from the analysis (both in terms of price measurement and discounting). This rough estimate should not be taken literally, but it does in any case indicate that the gains of commuting are relatively low in the larger context.

In Table B-29 to Table B-38, we have considered how the regional work distribution in Coastal Southern Norway's subregions¹⁰ has changed over industries before and after 2008. This enables us to consider potential regional composition effects for employment caused by the renewal of European Route 18 between Kristiansand and Grimstad, which opened August 2009. The tables show that Kristiansand has a relatively high labor cost level in most industries. This is of course partly due to differences in education level, but also reflects labor compensation capability. The overall picture is that there have been obvious welfare-improving reallocations between Kristiansand and its Eastern suburbs after the road opening at European Route 18, which is visible at macro level.

For consumer and material manufacturing, wholesale and vehicle trade, transportation and tourism, Kristiansand experienced a weaker employment growth than its eastern suburbs after 2008. In the case of tourism, Kristiansand's employment development has admittedly been considerably weaker in the previous years. Within technological manufacturing, Kristiansand has had a very strong employment growth across the whole study period, whereas its eastern suburbs experience a strong decline. Also, within knowledge consultancy, the employment growth was stronger in Kristiansand than in its eastern suburbs both before and after 2008.

¹⁰ To make the analysis transparent, we have classified Coastal Southern Norway into six subregions; Northeastern Agder (Risør and Tvedestrand), Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand (Arendal, Grimstad and Lillesand), Kristiansand city (Kristiansand), Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand (Birkenes, Lindesnes, Mandal, Songdalen, Søgne and Vennesla), Lister periphery (Kvinesdal and Lyngdal) and Lister towns (Farsund and Flekkefjord).

The retail trade industry in Kristiansand’s eastern suburbs had a relatively poor development subsequent to the opening of European Route 18, supporting the hypothesis that the industry was subject to composition effects. Yet, the retail industry in Kristiansand did not grow particularly much in the same period. Within information service, Kristiansand experienced a strong growth after 2008, while the city’s eastern suburbs experienced a sharp decline, which could be a sign of relocation of this industry. Yet, the labor costs level in Kristiansand was not particularly high compared to Arendal, Grimstad and Lillesand in this period. In addition, the development in this industry is likely to have been affected by the relocation of the Norwegian Communications Authority to Lillesand in 2007. In case of business support, Kristiansand’s employment share grew from 2008 to 2014, but apparently this was at the expense of the northern and western suburbs, not its eastern suburbs. Besides, the labor cost level in Kristiansand was below the regional average for this particular industry.

Welfare-improving composition effects at regional level may also occur, if spare employment becomes utilized to a larger extent. As oil and gas suppliers have had a very strong activity growth over the study period, we add a control for the supply industry’s activity levels to our baseline estimation framework subsection 2.4. For a municipality at a given time, we set the control for oil and gas suppliers’ local activity levels equal to lagged industry employment with the industry’s national employment growth.¹¹ In Table B-39, we have presented our results on how increased market access caused by expansion in the road network has affected different employment and population variables. We generally find little support that regional integration through road constructions has contributed positively to the local employment levels. On the other hand, the municipalities next to new road construction seem to have experienced strong employment growth before the associated openings.

Not even the regression for outgoing commuting involves positive impact estimates from increased market access through expansions in the road network, although these estimates are significantly higher than the placebo development. Yet, readers should bear in mind that the municipality experiencing the highest increase in market access – Lillesand – received a contrary shock in the establishment of the Norwegian Communications Authority in the municipality in 2007. It may also be the case that the true distance decay parameters are lower than the ones applied for commuting, which would have involved more weight on regional integration of municipalities along European Route 18 further away from Kristiansand, such as Grimstad and Arendal. In addition, the decrease in traveling time could involve a non-symmetric impact, where potential commuters perceive traveling time reductions well above ten minutes differently than traveling time reductions well below. Although there may be some hold in these explanations of the insignificant impact estimates, our results clearly suggest that one should not overestimate potential positive impulses from road openings on the efficiency of the regional work division through commuting.

¹¹ Formally, the oil and gas supply control for municipality i at time t , $z_{i,t}^{pet}$, is given by $z_{i,t}^{pet} = \ln \left(l_{i,t-1}^{pet} * \frac{l_t^{pet}}{l_{t-1}^{pet}} \right)$, where $l_{i,t}^{pet}$ is the number of persons employed in connection to the oil and gas industry in municipality i at time t and l_t^{pet} is the number of persons employed in connection to the oil and gas industry in the municipality in the whole country at time t . We refer to subsection 3.1 for details on identification of this cluster employment.

Commuting patterns		Pre-treatment status for commuting shares		Treatment status for commuting shares		Growth in outgoing commuting shares		Commuting gains given industry structure	
Workplace	Residence	Level	Share	Level	Share	Actual	Adjusted	Raw	Adjusted
European Route 18 – Kristiansand-Grimstad (Pre-treatment years: 2004-2008. Treatment years: 2010-2010)									
Kristiansand	Risør	40.2	1.3 %	53.6	1.7 %	0.4 %	0.4 %	1.13	1.04
	Tvedestrand	51.4	1.8 %	56.6	2.0 %	0.2 %	0.1 %	1.31	1.11
	Arendal	542.4	2.8 %	809.2	3.9 %	1.1 %	1.1 %	1.10	1.05
	Grimstad	448.9	4.7 %	889.6	8.5 %	3.7 %	3.6 %	1.05	1.02
	Lillesand	1 174.6	25.5 %	1 455.7	28.9 %	3.4 %	2.8 %	1.02	1.01
	Birkenes	464.9	21.3 %	589.2	23.9 %	2.6 %	2.1 %	1.19	1.03
Risør		7.6	0.0 %	15.0	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.90	1.00
Tvedestrand		2.2	0.0 %	6.8	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.81	1.00
Arendal	Kristiansand	189.1	0.5 %	340.6	0.8 %	0.3 %	0.3 %	0.90	1.00
Grimstad		160.7	0.4 %	188.4	0.4 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.95	1.00
Lillesand		289.3	0.7 %	554.2	1.3 %	0.6 %	0.5 %	0.93	1.00
Birkenes		101.4	0.3 %	110.4	0.3 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.85	1.00
Arendal	Lillesand	154.1	3.3 %	176.7	3.5 %	0.2 %	0.2 %	0.91	1.00
	Birkenes	54.3	2.5 %	52.6	2.1 %	-0.4 %	-0.3 %	1.04	1.01
	Lillesand	216.1	4.7 %	217.1	4.3 %	-0.4 %	-0.2 %	0.95	1.00
Grimstad	Birkenes	56.9	2.6 %	59.1	2.4 %	-0.2 %	-0.1 %	0.93	1.00
Lillesand	Arendal	6.0	0.6 %	18.4	1.1 %	0.5 %	0.5 %	1.00	1.00
	Grimstad	28.2	2.8 %	66.2	3.8 %	1.0 %	1.0 %	0.95	1.00
Birkenes	Arendal	0.3	0.1 %	0.4	0.1 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.93	1.00
	Grimstad	2.0	0.5 %	2.0	0.4 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.89	1.00
European Route 39 – Flekkefjord-Lyngdal (Pre-treatment years: 2004-2008. Treatment years: 2010-2010)									
Flekkefjord	Lyngdal	24.0	0.7 %	63.5	1.6 %	1.0 %	1.0 %	0.99	1.00
Lyngdal	Flekkefjord	22.5	0.5 %	39.5	0.9 %	0.3 %	0.4 %	0.83	1.00
County Route 465 in Vest-Agder – Farsund-Kvinesdal (Pre-treatment years: 2004-2008. Treatment years: 2013-2014)									
Farsund	Kvinesdal	23.2	0.9 %	40.0	1.4 %	0.5 %	0.6 %	1.01	1.00
Kvinesdal	Farsund	30.9	0.7 %	59.0	1.2 %	0.6 %	0.7 %	1.15	1.05

Table B-28: Changes in outgoing commuting in relation to major road openings in Coastal Southern Norway with additional depiction of approximated commuting gains. Pre-treatment years: 2004 to 2008. Treatment years: 2010 to 2014. Adjustment in outgoing commuting shares adjusts for employment growth in the working municipalities unrelated to the commuting from the pinpointed municipalities that have become more integrated with them. Commuting gains are calculated as the ratio between the labor cost levels in the workplace and residence municipalities, where the aggregate industries' contributions to the labor cost levels for the workplace municipality are weighted in accordance with their employment share in the residence municipality. Adjustments in relative labor cost level involve subtraction of commuting traveling costs and bounding of commuting gains from a lower bound set to zero to an upper bound set to the reduction in private traveling time costs with mark-ups for labor income tax and pay roll taxes.

Regional composition effects could also attract more fixed capital to the region, if such investments become relatively profitable until the new profit opportunities are exhausted. This is particularly the case for mobile fixed capital, which can be relocated through new areas subsequent to the initial investments.¹² In Table B-10, we report our results on how increased market access through road constructions has affected the regional fixed capital holdings, still

¹² We measure mobile fixed capital as the sum of 'machinery', 'equipment', 'small means of transportation', 'large means of transportation and mobile production units', 'research and development', 'patents' and 'cultivated biological resources'. Immobile fixed capital is measured as the sum of 'land area', 'buildings' and 'construction'.

applying control for oil and gas supply activities. The results give no indications of positive impulses on fixed capital from road openings. There are even signs of negative local impacts on the capital holdings, when all industries are included. Possible explanations for these results include the construction activities associated with the new roads and relatively strong price developments and heterogeneous performance in industry activities associated with oil and gas.

Figure B-3: Outgoing commuting rates within a) Southern Aust-Agder (l.h.s) and b) Lister Region (r.h.s.) in 2004, 2008 and 2014 with depiction of road opening (blue color) and no expansion (green color)

Impact on employment Time dimension Region \ period	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
	Average status	Average status	Annual growth	Annual growth
	2004-2008	2004-2008	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	0.9835	0.0335	0.0152	-0.0224
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	1.0860	0.2188	-0.0165	0.0332
Kristiansand city	1.0546	0.5062	-0.0146	-0.0568
Northern and western suburbs of Kristiansand	0.8709	0.1450	0.0278	0.0683
Lister periphery	0.5151	0.0439	0.0026	-0.0119
Lister towns	0.9282	0.0527	-0.0144	-0.0104

Table B-29: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within consumer manufacturing in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Impact on employment	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
Time dimension	Average status	Average status	Annual growth	Annual growth
Region \ period	2004-2008	2004-2008	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	0.8302	0.0842	0.0108	0.0020
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	0.9623	0.1492	-0.0186	-0.0188
Kristiansand city	1.0849	0.2377	0.0512	-0.0353
Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand	1.0189	0.2865	-0.0082	-0.0274
Lister periphery	0.9107	0.1381	0.0358	-0.0034
Lister towns	1.0657	0.1042	-0.0711	0.0828

Table B-30: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within material manufacturing in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Impact on employment	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
Time dimension	Status	Status	Growth	Growth
Region \ period	2004	2004	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	0.9050	0.0203	0.0042	-0.0087
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	0.8207	0.3573	-0.0920	-0.0832
Kristiansand city	1.2866	0.3559	0.0908	0.1626
Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand	0.8882	0.1652	-0.0081	-0.0350
Lister periphery	0.7561	0.0247	-0.0020	-0.0315
Lister towns	0.8109	0.0765	0.0071	-0.0042

Table B-31: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within technological manufacturing in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Impact on employment	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
Time dimension	Average status	Average status	Annual growth	Annual growth
Region \ period	2004-2008	2004-2008	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	0.9210	0.0172	0.0030	-0.0036
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	0.9464	0.2986	-0.0147	0.0211
Kristiansand city	1.0677	0.4950	0.0064	-0.0595
Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand	0.9514	0.1046	0.0067	0.0446
Lister periphery	0.8786	0.0487	-0.0084	0.0031
Lister towns	0.8623	0.0359	0.0070	-0.0057

Table B-32: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within wholesale and vehicle trade in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Impact on employment	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
Time dimension	Average status	Average status	Annual growth	Annual growth
Region \ period	2004-2008	2004-2008	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	1.0350	0.0392	0.0030	0.0049
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	1.0250	0.3057	0.0082	-0.0268
Kristiansand city	0.9859	0.3824	-0.0020	0.0017
Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand	0.9833	0.1523	-0.0135	0.0155
Lister periphery	0.9825	0.0591	0.0044	0.0047
Lister towns	1.0053	0.0611	-0.0001	0.0000

Table B-33: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within retail trade in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Impact on employment	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
Time dimension	Average status	Average status	Annual growth	Annual growth
Region \ period	2004-2008	2004-2008	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	0.7999	0.0301	-0.0160	-0.0106
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	1.0108	0.3195	-0.0075	-0.0173
Kristiansand city	1.0686	0.4398	0.0187	-0.0639
Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand	0.7977	0.1213	0.0017	0.0961
Lister periphery	0.9346	0.0384	-0.0067	0.0123
Lister towns	1.0222	0.0509	0.0099	-0.0166

Table B-34: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within transportation in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Impact on employment	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
Time dimension	Average status	Average status	Annual growth	Annual growth
Region \ period	2004-2008	2004-2008	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	0.8807	0.0444	0.0021	-0.0069
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	0.9426	0.2503	0.0492	-0.0083
Kristiansand city	1.0696	0.5258	-0.0670	-0.0088
Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand	0.7976	0.0820	0.0099	0.0001
Lister periphery	1.0456	0.0408	0.0182	0.0206
Lister towns	1.0135	0.0566	-0.0124	0.0033

Table B-35: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within tourism in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Impact on employment Time dimension Region \ period	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
	Average status	Average status	Annual growth	Annual growth
	2004-2008	2004-2008	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	0.7419	0.0142	-0.0017	-0.0006
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	1.0349	0.3507	0.0492	-0.1058
Kristiansand city	1.0173	0.5271	-0.0430	0.1207
Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand	0.8896	0.0589	0.0073	-0.0161
Lister periphery	0.6579	0.0120	-0.0031	-0.0010
Lister towns	0.7916	0.0371	-0.0088	0.0028

Table B-36: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within information services in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Impact on employment Time dimension Region \ period	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
	Average status	Average status	Annual growth	Annual growth
	2004-2008	2004-2008	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	0.8217	0.0271	0.0057	-0.0004
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	0.9663	0.2382	-0.0366	-0.0267
Kristiansand city	1.0769	0.5654	0.0220	0.0117
Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand	0.7679	0.0905	0.0214	0.0041
Lister periphery	0.8677	0.0180	0.0000	0.0042
Lister towns	0.8783	0.0608	-0.0124	0.0070

Table B-37: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within knowledge consultancy in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Impact on employment Time dimension Region \ period	Relative labor cost level		Employment share	
	Average status	Average status	Annual growth	Annual growth
	2004-2008	2004-2008	2004-2008	2008-2014
Northeastern Agder	0.8858	0.0290	-0.0220	0.0066
Eastern suburbs of Kristiansand	1.0568	0.2085	0.0316	0.0005
Kristiansand city	0.9635	0.6083	-0.0279	0.0362
Northern and Western suburbs of Kristiansand	1.1169	0.1432	0.0243	-0.0433
Lister periphery	0.9433	0.0037	-0.0009	0.0032
Lister towns	1.0638	0.0073	-0.0050	-0.0032

Table B-38: Annual growth employment shares in single- and multi-branch firms across municipalities within business support in Coastal Southern Norway measured by percentage points with additional depiction of average relative labor costs and initial employment shares. Relative positive growth in regional labor shares is indicated by green color.

Industry \ Study region	Impact on firm size							
	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
Distance decay	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Total population	0.108 (0.075)	0.056 (0.110)	0.069 (0.118)	0.055 (0.111)	0.720*** (0.196)	0.651*** (0.166)	0.922*** (0.091)	0.680*** (0.082)
Population at working age (20 to 66 years)	-0.031 (0.094)	-0.059 (0.126)	-0.102 (0.130)	-0.083 (0.117)	0.841*** (0.114)	0.760*** (0.111)	0.908*** (0.085)	0.622*** (0.110)
Total employment by residence	0.126 (0.092)	0.082 (0.132)	-0.002 (0.146)	-0.002 (0.127)	1.307*** (0.148)	1.210*** (0.111)	1.229*** (0.093)	0.933*** (0.062)
Employment by residence, more than two years' higher education	0.192 (0.136)	0.142 (0.184)	-0.024 (0.191)	-0.012 (0.158)	1.210*** (0.313)	1.082*** (0.250)	1.013*** (0.132)	0.754*** (0.100)
Employment by residence, less than two years' higher education	0.029 (0.089)	-0.011 (0.119)	-0.072 (0.130)	-0.074 (0.114)	1.387*** (0.200)	1.286*** (0.167)	1.296*** (0.109)	0.992*** (0.077)
Total employment by workplace	0.556*** (0.160)	0.300 (0.293)	0.238 (0.302)	0.121 (0.248)	1.391*** (0.448)	1.036** (0.355)	1.790*** (0.174)	1.290*** (0.121)
Employment in selected industries for all firms	0.956** (0.422)	0.238 (0.749)	-0.024 (0.555)	-0.239 (0.457)	0.282 (1.004)	0.169 (0.827)	1.141** (0.524)	0.818* (0.424)
Employment in selected industries for single-branch firms	0.060 (0.371)	-0.196 (0.541)	0.092 (0.665)	0.509 (0.817)	2.176 (1.630)	2.097 (1.213)	1.512* (0.765)	1.272** (0.591)
Incoming commuter rate of employment by workplace	0.341*** (0.063)	0.221* (0.123)	0.190* (0.110)	0.119 (0.107)	0.171 (0.192)	0.019 (0.182)	0.339*** (0.069)	0.206*** (0.062)
Outgoing commuter rate of employment by residence	0.051 (0.038)	0.053 (0.045)	0.031 (0.045)	0.034 (0.044)	-0.075 (0.185)	-0.047 (0.157)	-0.112 (0.068)	-0.0935* (0.050)
Registered unemployment rate	-0.023* (0.011)	-0.016 (0.017)	0.013 (0.016)	0.015 (0.013)	-0.150 (0.137)	-0.146 (0.105)	-0.066* (0.035)	-0.035 (0.031)
Share of population at working age outside the labor force	0.066*** (0.015)	0.060* (0.029)	0.046** (0.018)	0.037* (0.021)	0.205*** (0.055)	0.195*** (0.043)	0.151*** (0.047)	0.144*** (0.047)

Table B-39: Impact and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on municipal population and employment measures, estimated by linear panel data regressions using municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). Core region: Coastal Southern Norway. Extended region: Coastal Southern Norway and municipalities in neighboring counties not located next to road openings. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

Impact on firm size Distance decay Industry \ Study region	Impact				Placebo			
	Core		Extended		Core		Extended	
	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.	Power	Exp.
Total fixed capital services all industries	-3.866*** (0.802)	-2.921** (1.234)	-1.389 (1.084)	-0.605 (1.193)	1.772 (5.245)	1.737 (4.801)	2.122* (1.219)	2.037** (0.889)
Total fixed capital stock, all industries	-4.502*** (1.113)	-3.425** (1.570)	-2.007* (1.155)	-1.000 (1.297)	1.583 (7.422)	1.511 (6.820)	1.372 (1.561)	1.416 (1.152)
Fixed capital stock for mobile capital, all industries	-1.868 (1.228)	-1.639 (1.141)	0.282 (1.084)	0.630 (1.404)	-4.605* (2.519)	-5.281** (1.956)	0.363 (1.489)	0.916 (1.201)
Fixed capital stock for immobile capital, all industries	-4.693** (1.717)	-3.523 (2.110)	-2.695** (1.075)	-1.536 (1.231)	8.801 (9.487)	9.023 (9.053)	4.458 (3.043)	3.446 (2.278)
Total fixed capital services selected industries	1.061 (0.673)	0.424 (1.101)	1.001 (0.847)	0.944 (1.003)	-0.705 (4.042)	-1.262 (3.190)	0.529 (1.775)	0.604 (1.452)
Total fixed capital stock, selected industries	0.943 (0.704)	0.309 (1.129)	1.221 (0.911)	1.147 (1.047)	0.010 (4.418)	-0.355 (3.493)	1.073 (1.853)	0.879 (1.463)
Fixed capital stock for mobile capital, selected industries	1.591** (0.704)	0.418 (1.260)	0.792 (0.901)	0.527 (1.028)	0.198 (3.305)	-0.521 (2.517)	-0.167 (1.945)	0.171 (1.739)
Fixed capital stock for immobile capital, selected industries	0.554 (1.062)	0.492 (1.356)	1.193 (0.881)	1.174 (0.967)	-0.239 (5.567)	-0.118 (4.504)	2.735 (2.347)	1.822 (1.742)

Table B-40: Impact and placebo impacts of increased market access caused by traveling time reduction on fixed capital service measures, estimated by linear panel data regressions using municipality fixed effects and clustered standard errors on municipalities. Market access is measured with power distance decay ($\delta^{pow} = 2.3$) and exponential distance decay ($\delta^{exp} = 0.07$). Core region: Coastal Southern Norway. Extended region: Coastal Southern Norway and municipalities in neighboring counties not located next to road openings. (* for $p < 0.1$, ** for $p < 0.05$ and * for $p < 0.01$)**

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